

Methodological Handbook

SYREALITY

سيريااليتي

Chapter 2: The SYREALITY Survey (Wave 1)

Version 4.0 (September 2025)

Lea Müller-Funk and Weam Ghabash

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Der Wissenschaftsfonds.

Website

<https://syreality.com/>

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Introduction

The SYREALITY project wants to learn about the outlook of people from Syria in Europe, specifically about their life plans, their experiences in Europe and challenges they have faced. SYREALITY collects individual survey data in Austria, Germany, the Netherlands, and Greece as well as life history interviews and cognitive maps in Vienna, Berlin, Amsterdam, and Athens. More specifically, the project aims to understand:

- How did Syrian forced migrants in Europe envision their future lives before the conflict, and how do they pursue or discard these plans in the face of war and continuing displacement?
- How do unfulfilled or newly forged life aspirations influence forced migrants' displacement trajectories and migration, return, and stay aspirations?
- How are life aspirations and displacement trajectories linked to social class?

SYREALITY collects and analyses a large amount of data in different forms across four countries (Austria, Germany, the Netherlands, Greece). The project generates the following types of new research data: (i) a survey data set (one wave); (ii) audio material and transcripts of approx. 100 life history interviews (two waves); (iii) cognitive maps which will be drawn as part of the qualitative interviews. Participants in the research project are defined as people born in Syria and/or holding Syrian nationality, having left Syria to Europe after 2011, and living in one of the four countries. The project also reuses the research data generated by the SYRMAGINE project (2017-2019) led by the principal investigator (PI) of SYREALITY, thus an individual survey data set (n=757) and 41 in-depth interviews collected with Syrians living in Tripoli, Beirut (Lebanon), Istanbul and Izmir (Turkey) in 2018.

The SYREALITY Methodological Handbook aims at documenting the methodological strategy and making the data collection process openly accessible. The chapters are living documents which were started during fieldwork preparation and evolved during fieldwork preparation, data collection and data cleaning. Chapter 1 elaborates on data management. Chapter 2 focuses on the SYREALITY survey and the quantitative data set. Chapter 3 elaborates on the qualitative data collection (life histories and cognitive maps). Subchapter 2.1 provides insights into research ethics related to the SYREALITY survey, its sampling strategy, quality assurance mechanisms, and the development of the survey instrument. Subchapter 2.2 discusses data collection and subchapter 2.3. data cleaning.

Chapter 2.1. Sampling strategy, research ethics, quality assurance, and survey questionnaire

2.1.1. Research design and sampling strategy

We aimed to draw a survey sample of Syrians who have settled in four countries (Austria, Germany, the Netherlands, Greece) since 2011 of around 1000 respondents in total (approx. 250 per country) through online convenience sampling. Developing an appropriate sampling design was part of the SYREALITY

project as sampling frames and possibilities to access contact details of potential respondents from national authorities diverge across countries. In September 2022, the PI organised a workshop in the frame of the SYREALITY project entitled “Surveying refugees and hard-to-reach populations in Europe and beyond: Comparing lessons learned”, which brought researchers together who conducted single-country, cross-national and/or longitudinal survey research among migrants, asylum-seekers and refugees in Europe, Africa, and the Middle East over the past years. The objective of the workshop was to provide an open space to present survey designs and fieldwork observations and discuss lessons learned and recommendations for designing longitudinal cross-national surveys with hard-to-reach populations such as migrants in refugees in Europe and beyond in the future. The surveys presented included the Displaced Persons in Austria Survey, the REHEAL Survey in Greece, the Social Integration and Mental Well-Being Survey in Austria, the TRAFIG Survey, the MIGNEX Survey, the SYRMAGINE Survey, a Longitudinal Survey on the Impact of the War in Ukraine on Displacement Patterns, Challenges in Displacement and Intentions to Returns, the longitudinal WELLCOME Survey (Germany), the New Status-Holders in the Netherlands Survey, the FIMAS Survey (Austria), an Online Survey of Ukrainian Refugees (OSUR), and the MOBILISE Survey.

After the exploration of different approaches to sampling refugees and hard-to-reach populations and their different trade-offs (esp. Poetzke 2022, Ersanilli & van der Gaag 2021), we decided to opt for an online survey with convenience sampling via Facebook advertising. It provides a cost-effective way of reaching different groups of Syrian refugees across four European countries but also allows easily to reach out for potential future waves. Syrians in Europe are well connected on social media and use Facebook extensively (Dekker et al. 2018) Access to electricity and the internet is not a problem – in contrast to the situation in Syria or Syria’s neighbouring countries. Participants will therefore be surveyed online and recruited into the sample through Facebook advertising between February and March 2023. The project budget unfortunately does not allow us to draw from the general population register as other researchers did: In Sweden, for example, a survey among persons from Syria granted residency drew the sample from the Total Population Register (Okenwa-Emegwa et al. 2019; Sengoelge et al. 2019). Similarly, the NSN panel survey among Syrian refugees and asylum-seekers could base their random sample on the Dutch Personal Records Database. Given our targeted age group (age 27-65), we decided to only focus on Facebook advertising and not include Instagram advertising which we might have considered in case of a younger targeted age group. We might consider additional offline convenience sampling during the qualitative fieldwork in community locations in Vienna, Berlin, Amsterdam, and Athens (such as NGOs, language class locations, mosques, restaurants, markets) in case the sample recruited through Facebook is highly biased when it comes to educational levels.

Online strategies

As a first step, we set up a bilingual Facebook page for the SYREALITY project in Arabic and English. The pinned post at the top of the page offers a short description of the SYREALITY project in English and Arabic. Our main concern was on the one hand to increase the trust of potential survey respondents as Syrians in Europe are also in the watchful eye of the Syrian regime. To increase legitimacy, we added bilingual posts

to the Facebook pages prior to launching the ads. We also added the project logo as profile picture and the university logo and the logo of the Austrian Science Fund to the title photo to show that the project is linked to a university.

Our second concern was to choose a positive and politically neutral visual representation of the research project. We designed two images with the help of a Syrian graphic designer which speak to ideas of hope and the future and avoid symbols of the uprising and the conflict. Our aim was to design visuals which spark potential respondents' interest on Facebook and make them want to participate in the study and the online survey. We wanted the visuals to be a positive representation (i) speaking to individual ideas and aspirations about the future, such as education, family, rights, and migration; (2) speaking to Syrians in the four country cases while avoiding symbols that represent one specific political side of the Syrian conflict (like the Syrian official flag (regime) or the flag used by the opposition). We therefore used the map of Syria, the Arabic word for Syria, Yasmin flowers (the national flower of Syria) and a mosaic as a symbol of Syrian culture.

We then designed the Facebook ads for the advertisement campaign to be run in February 2023 following the recommendations by Ersanilli and van der Gaag (2021) and Pötzschke (2022). We will prolong the advertisement campaign in case we do not reach our targeted sample size. The goal of the advertisements is to generate clicks on an external link (the LimeSurvey website hosting the SYREALITY survey): The link in the ad leads respective users to the start screen of our online survey. Facebook calls this campaign objective "Send people to your website." Following Pötzschke and Braun's (2017) and Ersanilli and van der Gaag's (2021) experiences and recommendations, we chose "traffic" as campaign objective for the Facebook ads. Under this campaign objective, the Facebook algorithm detects which kind of users are most likely to click on the ad and shows the ad to users with a similar profile (Neundorf and Öztürk 2021).

An important feature of Facebook ads is that they can be used to target specific subpopulations within the users of the network. Facebook also allows specifying locations and how users should be related to them. Given our targeted group, we set the minimum age to 27 and the maximum age to 65. Regarding the sex of targeted users, we chose "all" for the survey. We included Austria, Germany, the Netherlands, and Greece with the option "people living in this location." The Facebook manager does not provide indicators identifying refugees nor expat ("Lived in ...") indicators for Syria. Direct targeting through the Facebook manager was therefore not possible. However, in the category behaviours, Facebook offers the option that the ads should only be displayed to individuals who were "away from hometown" and who "live abroad", which we specified. We also specified "Arabic" under languages. We unfortunately could not specify a local variant of Arabic (Syrian Arabic). Based on these specifications, Facebook estimated our audience size at 456,700 - 537,300.

We thus had to additionally target Syrian refugees via the images and wording of the ads when we then designed the Facebook ads. Facebook ads consist of a headline, body text, link description and image. Our ads use minimal text and images. We decided to use a neutral wording in the headline and body text, which included the country of origin, the country of residence (and a time frame) instead of including the word "refugee" in the ad. A link redirects users to the Arabic version of the survey on the LimeSurvey

platform hosted by the University for Continuing Education Krems. We designed two ads with identical text and two different images to account for differences in visual taste in English and Arabic. The images invite potential survey respondents to participate in the survey via a symbol representing a survey or the Arabic word for survey and included the university logo to increase credibility. The ad for the SYREALITY survey reads:

Headline: Syrians in Europe

Body text: Are you from Syria and live in Germany, Austria, the Netherlands, or Greece? Participate in a research project by answering our survey!

Link description: Participate in our survey!

Call to action: Learn more

Headline: السوريون في أوروبا

Primary text: هل أنت من سوريا وتعيش في ألمانيا أو النمسا أو هولندا أو اليونان؟ شارك في مشروع بحث من خلال استبياننا!

Link description: شارك في استبياننا

Call to action: Learn more

Ad version 1

Syreality Project - مشروع
سيرياليتي
Sponsored · 🌐

هل أنت من سوريا وتعيش في ألمانيا أو النمسا أو هولندا أو اليونان؟
شارك في مشروع بحث من خلال استبياننا!

استبيان
آمال وتطلعات السوريين

uwk-krems.limesurvey.net
السوريون في أوروبا
شارك في استبياننا!

Learn more

Like Comment Share

Ad version 2

Syreality Project - مشروع
سيرياليتي
Sponsored · 🌐

هل أنت من سوريا وتعيش في ألمانيا أو النمسا أو هولندا أو اليونان؟
شارك في مشروع بحث من خلال استبياننا!

آمال وتطلعات السوريين

uwk-krems.limesurvey.net
السوريون في أوروبا
شارك في استبياننا!

Learn more

Like Comment Share

2.1.2. Research ethics

Prior to the fieldwork, the PI consulted the Ethics Advisory Board of the University for Continuing Krems (UWK) and received ethical approval of the survey. We acknowledged and agreed with the European Commission's Guidance Note on research on refugees, asylum seekers and migrants that research on refugees concerns a particularly vulnerable group which needs particular safeguards in terms of research ethics. Ethical issues involved are benefit-sharing potentials, cultural sensitivity, the recruitment of participants, informed consent, participants' safety and confidentiality. We were aware that the biggest risk in social science research relates to the disclosure of a person's identity and insufficient protection of private information, which is particularly important when studying a refugee population. The situation in Syria and the region was very volatile, and the respondents were vulnerable in many ways, from the government and other groups from Syria inside or outside the country, from the current host environment, and in relation to receiving asylum in European countries.

Informed consent

We obtained and documented informed consent from all survey respondents. For consent to be informed, potential respondents must understand what responding to the survey entails and voluntarily agree to it. The opening screen of the survey in LimeSurvey explained that participation is confidential and voluntary (see questionnaire). It referred people to the SYREALITY website for more information on the project and their rights via a Project Information Sheet which could be downloaded as a Pdf file from the introduction screen of the survey. Participants were also informed in the information sheet which data was collected as part of the survey and that they could withdraw from the study if they wished to do so later. To account for the sensitive nature of some parts of the survey, we included "prefer not to answer" or "no answer" options for all questions which we and/or our test respondents considered as sensitive. We also added "don't know" options to many questions to account for uncertainty in respondents' lives and decisions.

Personal data and quality assurance

The survey was collected through the LimeSurvey software, which was hosted at the University for Continuing Education Krems. The survey itself did not collect directly identifying data as part of the main survey. However, the GPS locations and contact details were recorded to check data quality and allow for follow-up interviews. The challenge with online survey, especially those recruited through advertisements, is that it is unclear who is participating in the survey. To get a rudimentary idea about the respondents, we enabled IP-address based geolocation in LimeSurvey as other researchers who have collected online surveys with (forced) migrants did (cf. Ersanilli and van der Gaag 2021). IP address and location information were deleted from the dataset before it is shared and finalised. This information was also removed from any future data deposit. The Project Information Sheet explained in the information sheet why IP addresses are collected and how they will be used.

The survey was designed to allow for future survey waves and qualitative follow-up interviews. At the end of the survey, respondents were asked if they were willing to participate in future surveys or a qualitative

interview and if so, to enter their preferred contact details. The contact details are solely used to contact participants for these two research purposes. The contact details and IP addresses were deleted from the survey data files and are stored separately in a Contact Database with a unique identifier and are removed from any future data deposit.

The survey also collected information which qualifies as ‘special categories of personal data’, e.g. questions on religion and language, which might give insight into ethnic affiliation, which are often sensitive. Including such topics obliges us to take particular care in data protection. The survey also collected data with the possibility of indirect identification as a result of unique and unusual combinations of responses. Unique and unusual responses will never be published in a way that would identify respondents. The survey data analysis will never focus on the individual level but will always be aggregated at some level.

Data protection and data management

Implementing an online survey means to take additional care of data protection. At the same time, it also offers strong measures to protect personal data. The LimeSurvey online survey platform is GDPR compliant as the server location is set to Germany (<https://www.limesurvey.org/support/faq/39-data-protection-and-policy>). Among others, this means that data are stored in a separate database with a separate username/password for each LimeSurvey Cloud instance. The connection is encrypted using SSL connections. A data protection declaration was prepared for the survey together with the data protection officer at UWK, positively assessed and added to the survey. A Data Management Plan (DMP) was submitted to the Austrian Science Fund and approved prior to the start of the project in October 2020 which was updated in October 2022 (see Methodological Handbook SYREALITY Chapter 1). The PI considers this DMP to be the first version of a living document which will evolve throughout the course of the project. A more detailed version will be drafted during the data analysis. Both versions are made openly accessible on the project website and on Zenodo.

2.1.3. Developing the survey questionnaire

Designing the survey instrument

The survey questionnaire was developed and tested between August and December 2022 together by the authors. Last changes were implemented in January 2023. The survey instrument draws from personal experiences from one of the two authors (Weam Ghabash) and insights from previous – especially qualitative – fieldwork by the PI (SYRMAGINE project; MAGYC project). It also draws from and partly adapts questions from existing surveys, such as the MIGNEX survey (Hagen-Zanker et al. 2020), the MOBILISE survey (Ersanilli and van der Gaag 2021), the SYRMAGINE survey, and other surveys measuring social stratification, such as the ESS, ISSP, and the QPLC (Qualifications, potentials and life courses of Syrian asylum seekers) survey. We also included recommendations from the MIGNEX survey that suggest using a 3-point scale and binary answers whenever possible. We initially considered designing a biographic life event survey based on the MAFE (*Migrations between Africa and Europe Project*) survey, which, however, would have been too long for an online survey, given its extensive length. The absence of an interviewer

makes online surveys more vulnerable to drop-out than face-to-face surveys. The SYREALITY questionnaire therefore uses a shortened questionnaire with an average length of 20min.

Core concepts and measurements

Syrian refugees in Europe: We decided not to use a legal definition of refugees in the survey. We instead define Syrian refugees in Europe as people who were born in Syria and/or hold Syrian nationality, left Syria after 2011 and currently live in one of the four country cases in Europe (Austria, Germany, Netherlands, Greece). This open definition allows us to include (i) Kurdish Syrians who might not have Syrian citizenship, (ii) Syrians who might have acquired a European citizenship in the meantime, and (iii) people who live with alternative residence permits in Europe (study, work permits) despite having left Syria after 2011. We decided to focus on the age group 27-65 (born between 1957 and 1996) – hence participants who were at least 15 years old when the uprising in Syria in 2011 took place. We considered 15 years to be an age when participants have first ideas about their broader life aspirations. Yet, this was also influenced by a practical concern to reduce potential language biases as we did not have the financial resources to translate the survey instrument into additional languages as mentioned above. We considered that participants who were at least 15 years old in 2011 to be more likely to have finished compulsory education in Arabic in Syria and hence be able to read Arabic.

Displacement trajectories: We define displacement trajectories in the survey as a change of residency over time across internal and international borders in the context of the Syrian conflict since March 2011 until the time of the survey, of which at least one part is perceived as being forced. We measure displacement trajectories through questions inquiring into all possible parts of displacement trajectories. These include questions about immobility, internal displacement, return movements, onward migration and internal migration within the current host country.

Time: Our objective was to inquire about the past, the present and the future and to design a survey instrument with having future waves in mind. We use three different time horizons in the first wave of the survey to account for changes over time: before 2011 (life before the conflict), between 2011 until respondents' arrival in Europe (life during the conflict in Syria and during potential displacement elsewhere), and between respondents' arrival in Europe and the moment when respondents fill out the survey instrument (life in Europe). We use distinct moments in time to help respondents remember these three time horizons given the long duration of the Syrian conflict and protracted displacement. We added an additional open question about key life events to understand which other key life events apart from conflict and displacement respondents considered to be crucial in their lives.

Life aspirations before and after conflict/displacement: Following de Haas (2021), we define life aspirations as people's perceptions of the 'good life' and emphasize that these perceptions (i) can relate to a wide variety of perceptions of what a good life might be and (ii) can be situated on different levels – on the individual level, they might be related to one's education, profession and prestige (social mobility), to the desire to live with or emotionally or financially support people we love and cherish; on the collective level, they can be about ideas about one's culture and religion, ideas of justice, political legitimacy and

ultimately about the kind of society people would like to live in. Linked to Emirbayer and Mische's conceptualisation of agency as a "temporally embedded process of social engagement, informed by the past but also oriented toward the future and toward the present" (Emirbayer and Mische 1998), we consider life aspirations to be based on the capacity of social actors to reactivate past patterns, imagine possible future, and make practical and normative judgments among alternative possible trajectories. Such capacities include the capacity to imagine the future realisation of life aspirations at home or elsewhere (see Müller-Funk, Üstübcici, Belloni forthcoming). To account for the changing nature of life aspirations, we measure life aspirations at three different point in time ((i) before 2011, (ii) between 2011 and leaving Syria and (iii) between arrival to Europe and now. The SYREALITY survey measures four types of life aspirations: (i) family/relationship aspirations (aspirations to live in a specific type of relationship or end a relationship), (ii) educational aspirations (aspirations to pursue a specific education), (iii) work aspirations (aspirations to pursue a specific career), (iv) aspirations for societal and political change in Syria (aspiration to change society and politics in Syria). While we did not specifically inquire into cultural aspirations, we included specific dimension of cultural aspirations within the four types of aspirations. For example, one reply option of the family / relationship aspiration question addresses social norms around relationships ("I wished to have a different romantic relationship than your family accepts"). Within the socio-political aspiration question, we included four follow-up questions inquiring into aspirations for changing gender roles and gender equality as one dimension of socio-cultural change.

Stay and migration aspirations: We define stay aspirations not only as the desire to remain home but also as the desire to re-empower oneself in a new environment. By doing this, we account for people who decide to stay home despite difficult circumstances and for those who renegotiate a place for themselves and their families in displacement. On the other end of the spectrum, we follow the work of Carling and Schewel (2018) and de Haas (2021) by defining migration aspirations as the conviction that migration is preferable to non-migration. We also conceptualize return aspirations and aspirations for onward migration as part of migration aspirations, even if they are subject to different political regimes and based on different motivations and constraints. In the survey instrument, we measured internal and international migration aspirations, return aspirations, and stay aspirations.

Stay and migration capabilities: We define "capabilities" as the personal capacity to act in the present – thus to realise aspirations in a specific structural context. In this sense, aspirations are not separated from capabilities as the capacity to imagine a better future at home or elsewhere is part a fundamental capability to act on the present. This personal capacity is certainly linked to economic, social, and cultural capital, as highlighted by several studies, but also depend on emotional resources such as positive cognition (such as hope) and risk tolerance. Building on the argument that migration and stay aspirations need to be considered to an equal degree, our conceptualisation of "capability" refers to the personal capacity to realise both, stay and migration (including return) aspirations, in a specific structural context (Müller-Funk, Üstübcici, Belloni forthcoming). We measured migration capabilities as "prepared to migrate but not been able to go" ("Since you arrived in this country, have you ever prepared to move to another country, but not been able to go?"), return capabilities as "considered to return but not been able to go" ("Some Syrians considered to return to Syria for different reasons. Have you ever considered to return but not been able to go?"), and stay capabilities as "wanted to stay but not been able to do so" ("Since you

left Syria until your arrival here, have you ever wanted to stay in a country in which you lived but not been able to do so?”).

Social class: We understand social class as a multifaceted concept incorporating objective socioeconomic positions, subjective positioning strategies, and self-perceptions with class positions being transnationally and individually (re-)negotiated (cf. Hunkler et al. 2022). Individuals within a social class are considered to share a similar ‘market situation’ and ‘work situation’. Accordingly, those individuals within a social class are thought to hold similar life chances and often lifestyles. Migrants generally perceive their social position as highly ambivalent (Engzell and Ichou 2019). Understanding the perceptions of changing social class position before and after displacement is a core challenge of the project. Existing research on social class in pre-war Syria (Longuenesse 1977; Cornand 1994; Vatter 1993; Schad 2013) shows that, historically, societies in the Middle East were characterised by a complex stratification with societies having been structured around an elite of notables (including major import-export merchants, descendants of noble lineages and high ranking *ulama*) at the top; a middle range of other merchants, artisans, lower *ulama*, professionals, and government officials; and a lower class of “commoners” of lesser income and status (journeyman artisans, day-labourers, and urban masses). Schad (2013) highlights the longstanding importance of – especially Aleppine – merchants for Syria’s bourgeoisie and the mixed character of the Syrian working class which builds on a long traditions of old craft corporations or guilds, with many Syrian workers being small proprietors of their own workshops.

There are different options to measure social class in social surveys – either social class schemes or social stratification scales (Ganzeboom and Treiman 2003), with most social surveys being based on Weberian approaches of social class rather than Marxist and Durkheimian approaches (Connelly et al. 2016, 4). The European Socioeconomic Classification (ESeC) was developed to facilitate cross-nationally comparative research. ESeC comprises a nine-class categorical measure, with recommended reduced versions of five or three classes, which can be readily operationalised from data coded into the three-digit version of the ISCO occupational unit group scheme. Social stratification scales place individuals at some point on a continuous or gradational one-dimensional hierarchy (easier for statistical modelling). The Social Interaction and Stratification Scales (CAMSIS) tend to be specific to particular societies; whereas the International Socio-Economic Index of Occupational Status (ISEI) and the Standard International Occupational Prestige Scale (SIOPS) are designed to be ‘universal’. The SIOPS provides a hierarchical ranking from the least to the most esteemed occupations according to average ratings, and scores are shown to correlate strongly with the socio-economic circumstances of individuals who hold these occupations. The ISEI by contrast calculates scores for occupations based on their average profiles in terms of the income and educational qualifications held by their incumbents (with some adjustment for age profiles) (Ganzeboom, de Graaf, and Treiman 1992).

We decided to measure social class in the survey in two ways: First, through a simplified collection of occupation based on Ganzeboom’s suggestions (Ganzeboom 2005; Züll 2016; Ganzeboom and Snow 2022). We had originally considered to use open questions for occupations and code these into the International Standard Classification of Occupations (ISCO codes, ILO 2010), which are widely used in international cross-national survey datasets (Connelly, Gayle and Lambert 2016). Combined with other

socio-economic measures, these codes can later be converted into social class schemes or social stratification scales. However, the instructions for open questions were considered too long and complicated by participants in the test runs and we decided to opt for a reduced number of categories and a follow-up question on type of employment (employed/self-employed). Furthermore, Ganzeboom and Sno concluded in 2022 that measurement of occupational status using a crude (showcard) format can be equally valid and (slightly) more reliable than measurement using a detailed open question format (such as commonly used). We slightly adapted the crude IISP classification categories following Ganzeboom's suggestions by including armed forces, which we considered crucial in a context of war.¹ For social class positions before 2011, we measure social class on the individual level through the longest occupation of each survey respondent before 2011. If the respondent had never done any paid work (because s/he was still too young/in school) and lives in a long-term partnership, we inquire into the longest occupation of his/her long-term partner before 2011. If the respondent had never done any paid work and did not live in a long-term partnership, we ask about the longest occupation of his or her father when the respondent was a teenager (aged 14). Second, we added a question on subjective social class rank based on research about situation-specific perceptions of social class in psychology (Kraus and Park 2014), using Adler et al's (2000) measure of subjective Socioeconomic Status (SES) to account for the fact that most of occupation-based measures were developed in contexts of the Global North and might not be accurate for the Syrian context. In this measure, participants indicate their position on a 10-rung ladder representing ascending levels of income, education, and occupation status in society. We measure social class positions at three different point in time in the survey (before 2011, at the moment of departure in Syria and at the moment of the survey).

Transnational ties: We define transnational ties as social, financial, and political ties across borders in the SYREALITY survey. These ties might induce social and political change in home societies or not (Portes 2010; Krawatzek and Müller-Funk 2020). We measure transnational ties in the survey through questions about (i) social contacts with family and friends in Syria and outside Europe, (ii) financial responsibilities for family members outside of Europe, (iii) aspirations for social and political change in Syria, and (iv) interest in politics in Syria. These questions were incorporated into the modules displacement (D) and life aspirations (ASP, FEMACT).

Emotions and mental well-being: We measure emotions and mental well-being in the survey with questions about respondents' general life satisfaction, satisfaction with mental health, and hope for the future (their own future in Europe and societal future in Syria).

¹ We included high army officers (majors and up) in the IISP classification category 2 (higher administrative), non-commissioned officers (lieutenants) in category 1 (professional and technical) and soldiers in the category 5 (service).

Survey modules

The survey consists of the following modules: Eligibility (E), Demographics 1 (DEM1), Life aspirations in the past and present (ASP), Displacement trajectory (D), Asylum policies (POL), Stay and migration aspirations, now and in the future (MIG), Demographics 2 (DEM2), Work, poverty, and wealth (WPW), Life satisfaction and hope (SAT), End (END). We decided to order the modules in a way that most important and easier to answer demographic variables (age, gender, educational attainment, marital status, children) come early in the survey to better understand survey breakoffs and to place more sensitive demographic variables (wealth, poverty, ethnicity measured via mother tongue, religious affiliation, income, social class) later in the survey to avoid earlier breakoffs due to sensitivity. We also decided to place an emotionally easier module (e.g. life aspirations) early in the survey and address respondents' displacement trajectory after that module. We also wanted to end the survey on a positive note, which is why we concluded the questionnaire with questions around hope and strategies to make oneself feel better.

2.1.4. Translating and testing the survey questionnaire

Given our targeted age group (27-65), respondents most probably finished compulsory education in Syria and were thus expected to be able to read Arabic. We first developed the survey in English and then translated it to Modern Standard Arabic by a native speaker (Weam Ghabash), while the PI checked if the Arabic translations matched the English version. We did not have the financial resources to add additional German, Dutch, and Greek versions. We tested the survey in Arabic in December 2022 with respondents who met our eligibility criteria and then adapted both versions (English and Arabic) based on the results of the testing. An incentive was paid for respondents of both interviews as a contribution for their time.

Translating the first version of the survey instrument

Difficulties in translating the first version of the survey evolved mostly around the question of how to translate the core concept of aspirations. We decided to use the term “strong wish” (رغبة شديدة) to refer to life aspirations in the questions of the survey instrument. In the Facebook ads and its visuals, we also use the term “aspirations” (تطلعات) and “hopes” (آمال). For migration and stay aspirations, we used the wording of the extensively tested MIGNEX survey instrument to measure migration aspirations to produce comparable survey data (“Would you like to go and live in another country sometime during the next five years, or would you prefer to stay [country of residence]?” | هل ترغب في الذهاب إلى بلد آخر والعيش فيه في وقت | (ما خلال السنوات الخمس المقبلة، أم تفضل البقاء في [النمسا / ألمانيا / هولندا / اليونان]؟). We translated return aspirations in a similar way (“Would you like to return to live in Syria in the next 5 years? | هل ترغب في العودة للعيش في (سورية في السنوات الخمس المقبلة؟). For return aspirations, we asked about a concrete time horizon (5 years) and a hypothetical return without a concrete time horizon (“in some point in the future in case it is safe”) based on previous research which emphasises that current and future return aspirations are fundamentally different categories (Müller-Funk and Fransen 2022).

Another key issue we discussed in depth when translating the first version of the survey was how to translate the term displacement to account for our definition but also how to inquire about respondents'

displacement trajectories in a sensitive way without reminding them about their potentially painful experiences of the asylum interview. We used the verb *nazaḥa* in Arabic which refers to moving to other lands but also to being displaced (in war), without a specification of whether displacement happens within or across borders, or without a specification of a legal status. We also decided to account for the forced nature of respondents' beginning of displacement trajectories and their stay aspirations in Syria via the following formulation: "I could not stay in Syria anymore because..." (لم أستطع البقاء في سوريا الآن... (...)) and asked about respondents' places of living inside and outside Syria.

Testing and adapting the survey instrument

We conducted two different types of tests: first, cognitive testing and second, a series of test runs of the survey questionnaire followed by an in-depth conversation about programming issues, difficulties, sensitivities, and inconsistencies in the questionnaire. Another key objective was to test if the questionnaire met the requirement of not exceeding 20min in length on average. We conducted two cognitive interviews and six test interviews.

Cognitive testing is a pretesting method used in order to expose response problems that are cognitive in origin. In the cognitive testing, we interviewed two respondents about their interpretation of questions and how they would produce an answer based on our questions. Conrad & Blair (2004) found that cognitive interviews uncovered more problems about the meanings of words and the logic of question than about time periods and task performance. The cognitive interviewees were asked to read the questions loudly and reflect on any issues they might encounter related to the questionnaire's clarity, sensitivity, programming, and whether they enjoyed the questionnaire in general. Each interview took between 90 to 120 minutes where we could detect three important issues: First, the formulation of some questions was perceived as insensitive, which we then adapted. For example, we replaced the word "private properties" in the introduction text of the section on Work, poverty, and wealth with "your economic situation". Given our section on political aspirations, which is sensitive in the Syrian context, one respondent urged us to highlight the fact that the project is conducted by a university by adding the university logo upfront and highlighting the privacy policy of the survey. Second, we encountered difficulties with the gender sensitive language in Arabic which we used in the initial translation as it was not familiar to respondents with low educational level and made the questionnaire much longer than expected. Third, we realised the need to modify some answer options of the multiple-choice questions by adding new options or by adjusting already existing ones so that the list better fits the Syrian context and makes the choices comprehensive for all respondents. For example, the initial question about educational levels did not completely reflect the different options of secondary schools in Syria. Similarly, the answer options of the question inquiring into whether respondents' education had been interrupted in Syria because of the war lacked some important alternative options (e.g. yes it was interrupted but respondents were able to pursue it in Syria or abroad afterwards). We also detected some language issues in the automatic Arabic translation of LimeSurvey, which we unfortunately could not modify ourselves. For example, the indication for the multiple-choice question "Check all that apply" was not translated correctly. We had to contact the technical support of LimeSurvey to correct the translation. As most interviewees in the test did not pay attention to the automatic indication of multiple-choice questions

(which appears below the question), we additionally added our own translation in brackets يمكنك اختيار (عدة خيارات) to the question to make sure that interviewees understand that they can give more than one answer.

After this round of cognitive testing, we incorporated the feedback into the questionnaire and proceeded with our test run. We conducted six test interviews with respondents of different gender, educational levels, and age. We first let respondents fill out the survey in our presence (online via Zoom or offline) and then had a follow-up in-depth conversation about which questions were difficult to understand or unpleasant to answer. We also measured the time of each survey run. While sharing the screen on Zoom, the interviewee of each session was asked to fill out the survey with real information about him/herself and ask the interviewer in case s/he has any questions. The interviewer's role was to observe the process and take notes about the raised questions, time duration, and any reactions she might notice. In general, the overall impression of the six interviewees about the questionnaire was very positive and filling out the questionnaire took as long as estimated. The interviews lasted around one hour – filling out the questionnaire took around the estimated duration (20 minutes) whereas introducing the survey and the follow-up discussion with the interviewee took the rest of the time.

Different issues were detected during this round of testing due to recruiting diverse interviewees from different social groups in terms of educational attainment, age, gender, and diverse aspirations for the future. These were mostly content related but also programming issues. For example, we replaced the word “exile” with “abroad” as the latter was clearer to respondents. One interviewee with low educational attainment also drew our attention to the need to reduce the amount of text on each screen so that he can read it more easily. The youngest interviewee found the question about his profession before 2011 not applicable since he was a child by then. We therefore added another answer option to account for this case. Another issue evolved around the question about general life satisfaction which we had formulated using the same wording as the SYRMAGINE survey (“How satisfied are you overall with your life these days?” | ما مدى رضاك بشكل عام عن حياتك هذه الأيام؟) to produce comparable data. We noticed that religious Muslim respondents might evaluate any life situation as good for them, given that, from a religious point of view, Muslims are supposed to accept any life situation as it is meant for their highest good. We therefore decided to include a second question (“In general, how are things going in your life nowadays?” | كيف تسير أمور حياتك بشكل عام هذه الأيام؟) to account for this possibility to (i) be able to compare the answers of the two life satisfaction questions but also to (ii) produce comparable data between the SYRMAGINE and SYREALITY survey.

Chapter 2.2. Data collection

The data collection of the survey lasted seven weeks and took place between 1 February and 22 March 2023. We decided to let the survey run for approximately two months to reach a sample size of approximately 2000 and ideally of at least 250 replies per country. Data collection coincided with the earthquake which hit Southeast Turkey and Northern Syria on 6 February 2023. This event will probably have an effect on how respondents replied to certain survey questions, especially the question about respondents' hope for Syria's future. The overall budget for the Facebook and Instagram ads amounted to 2,200 EUR, which makes sampling via social media a cost-effective strategy. We did not pay any incentives.

4,876 people opened the first page of the survey, 3,892 people passed the eligibility section of the survey and 1,962 people completed the survey until the last question. Overall, we received more responses in the first weeks of the data collection and fewer responses the longer the data collection lasted. For example, in the second week, we received 1,429 survey responses (of whom 589 completed the survey). In contrast, in the last week of the data collection, we received 385 new responses (of whom 164 completed the survey). In the later phase of data collection, we received around 30 full survey responses per day with a daily ad budget of 40 EUR. It was overall very difficult to receive survey responses from respondents in Greece, despite several attempts to target respondents in Greece more specifically. The ratio of respondents from Greece remained more or less stable since the beginning of data collection.

Advertisement campaigns

With our advertisement campaign, we specified a targeted audience via the Facebook Ad Manager, which we adjusted several times over the course of the data collection to increase the number of female respondents, the number of respondents from Greece and to attract younger age cohorts. While we did not include a gender quote in the survey we aimed to reach a female participation ratio which is roughly representative of the presence of Syrian women in the four countries. Overall, fewer Syrian women have sought refuge in Europe than Syrian men. While in neighbouring countries such as Jordan, Lebanon and Turkey, women account for roughly 50 % of all Syrian refugees, in Germany, for example, of the estimated 550,000 Syrian asylum seekers in Germany who arrived between 2011 and 2015, around three quarters of adults were men (Disrupted families 2018, 11). By October 2015, women comprised 18%, 12% and 15% of Syrian, Afghan and Iraqi asylum seekers in Europe respectively (UN Women 2023).²

With our first ad campaign, we included Austria, Germany, the Netherlands, and Greece with the option "people living in this location" and included people of all genders between the age of 27 and 65. We also specified "Arabic" under languages. We unfortunately could not specify a local variant of Arabic (Syrian Arabic). The Facebook manager does not provide indicators identifying refugees nor expat ("Lived in ...")

² "Women refugees and migrants", UN Women, Europe and Central Asia, <https://eca.unwomen.org/en/news/in-focus/women-refugees-and-migrants-0>, accessed: 15/03/2023.

indicators for Syria. Direct targeting through the Facebook manager was therefore not possible. However, in the category behaviours, Facebook offers the option that the ads should only be displayed to individuals who were “away from hometown” and who “live abroad”, which we specified. Based on these specifications, Facebook estimated our audience size at 456,700 - 537,300. We ran this ad in English and Arabic, which both linked to the Arabic version of the survey. These first two ads ran for two weeks.

After publishing these first ads, we started to receive the first survey responses. However, on the second day, Facebook restricted our page linked to the ads without indicating a reason, which meant that our ads stopped running. After requesting a review and contacting Facebook, the restriction was withdrawn after a couple of hours. On the third day, we also decided to manually hide respondents’ comments about the ads to prevent potential biases and open public discussions. Facebook and Instagram users can comment on ads and there is no function to generally hide comments on ads. We also switched off the function that people could publicly reply to our posts on the Facebook page. We instead suggested users to get in contact with us for any questions via the Messenger function. Some users interacted with our ads by pressing the "Like" button or leaving a comment. The comments reflected different perceptions of the survey and varied between friendly to aggressive opinion: Many visitors, for example, complimented the survey and asked for more information about the project. Others contacted us directly via Messenger feature to elaborate more about certain parts of their response, or to ask if they could be of any help for the project. On the other hand, there were also negative perceptions about the survey: First, users were suspicious that the survey could have an affiliation to the Syrian regime; second, users believed that the survey could make financial profits, and third, users were generally pessimist that the survey could make any positive change with regards to their living conditions. However, we could also see from the survey question about the overall impression of the survey that respondents in general approve of the survey. 1,672 out of 1,962 respondents who finished the survey agree to a follow-up survey questionnaire and 1,276 agreed to a follow-up qualitative interviews.

We adjusted our ads several times to deal with the initially low ratio of female participants and the uneven response rates among the four targeted countries on the one hand, and to include a larger targeted audience on the other hand. After the first week, we added two ads in Arabic with two different visuals which only targeted women (estimated audience size on Facebook: 147,300 - 173,300) and used the female verb and noun forms in Arabic for two weeks to test if this strategy could change the participation rate of women. We added another ad targeting especially women at the end of the data collection, which ran for two weeks. Through this strategy, the participation rate of women remained more or less stable at 30% throughout the data collection.

After the second week, we also linked an Instagram account to our Facebook page and also allowed ads to be run on Instagram. We thought that including ads on Instagram might better target younger age cohorts, as Facebook is more used by older cohorts and Instagram by younger cohorts. We managed to reach a good participation of all age groups between 27 and 65, with a higher share of younger age groups, which is however also representative of the overall Syrian refugee population in Europe.

In the third week, we also realised that the ad in Arabic worked much better than the ad in English (2,933 clicks versus 1,249 link clicks, see Table 1 below), which is why we decided to continue to run the ads solely in Arabic. We instead doubled the daily ad budget per ad. We also decided to use the same target audience as in the first two weeks but additionally used the function "advantage detailed targeting" to target respondents beyond our detailed targeting selections when is likely to improve performance. This decision increased our estimated audience size by Facebook to 1,100,000 - 1,200,000. In the fifth week, we tried to especially target respondents in Greece by placing an additional ad with a new headline ("Syrians in Greece"). However, this strategy did not change the overall ratio of respondents from Greece. The following table shows the different ad campaigns of the SYREALITY survey, their results (number of link clicks), their reach (number of Accounts Centre accounts that saw ads at least once), their impressions (number of times that the ads were on-screen), cost per results and the amount spent.

Table 1: Ad campaigns of the SYREALITY survey

Campaign name	Results	Reach	Impressions	Cost per results	Amount spent (EUR)	Ends
Syrians in Europe Arabic 0	2933	51069	123599	0,089383	262,16	2023-02-15
Syrians in Europe English 0	1249	34551	126203	0,213571	266,75	2023-02-15
Syrian in Europe Arabic wom	2471	36783	110812	0,103954	256,87	2023-02-20
Syrians in Europe Arabic 2	3869	81824	156397	0,061168	236,66	2023-02-23
Syrians in Europe Arabic 3	10535	167165	457927	0,081744	861,17	2023-03-22
Syrians in Greece Arabic 1	1108	11768	131962	0,126336	139,98	2023-03-10
Syrian in Europe Arabic wom	1589	36363	55642	0,11102	176,41	2023-03-22

As expected, the Arabic version of the questionnaire was ultimately much more successful, with 99,6 % of survey respondents choosing to use the Arabic version.

Overall, respondents were much more often referred to the survey via Facebook (93,8%) than Instagram (5,6%). A small number of respondents reached the survey via the project website (0,07%) or directly via the LimeSurvey website of the university (0,34%).

Potential biases and break-offs

Of the cleaned data set of the target population, 61,4% of survey respondents lived in Germany (2,366), 19,0% in the Netherlands (731), 15,0% in Austria (577), and 4,4% in Greece (170). This means that we did not reach our objective to reach a sample of 250 in Greece but had significantly bigger samples for the other three countries.

62,8% of survey respondents identified as men, 34,8% as women, 0,7% as other; 1,7% were missing. This reflects the fact that the Syrian refugee population in Europe is predominantly male; at the same time, we probably slightly oversampled women.

With regards to educational attainment, 3,0% of respondents had no formal education or had attained primary education (grade 1.6), 9,2% middle school (grade 7-9), 20,4% secondary school (grade 10-12), 17,8% a technical post-secondary certificate, 47,3% a university degree (BA, MA or PhD); 2,3% of responses were missing. While we probably oversampled people with high educational attainment, our sample also reflects the fact that migrant groups are often better educated than the origin population at the same

time. Syrians are no exception: Syrians in Europe are on average positively selected on education. Compared to other groups of migrants, Syrians come to Germany with higher levels of education and English language skills (Ashour 2022). Welker (2022) found, for example, that Syrians are the most positively selected group compared to other refugee populations such as from Iraq and Afghanistan: The median Syrian refugee in Germany is at least as educated as 76.6 % of the population at origin. According to recent data (Rich 2016, 5), 27.0% of Syrian adult asylum-seekers in Germany in 2015 had attended university, 26.6% high school, 26.6% middle school and 17.4% primary school. Many Syrians also continued their education upon their arrival in Europe, which had been interrupted due to the conflict in Syria.

Out of the targeted population, our survey encountered a break-off rate of 49,4%. Most break-offs happened after the eligibility section, probably when respondents had gained a better understanding over the topic of the survey and in the first section on life aspirations. Roughly half of those belonging to the target population completed the survey in full (50,7%).

Our break-off rate is comparable to other online surveys (Peytchev 2009; Ersanilli and van der Gaag 2021; Pötzschke (workshop presentation Krems, September 2022)). Pötzschke, for example, reported for his online survey with Ukrainians conducted in 2022 that less than half of those who started the survey completed the survey (presentation Krems, September 2022). In the online survey, which Ersanilli & van der Gaag (2021, 22) conducted, roughly a third of respondents belonging to the target group completed the survey in full. The high educational attainment levels of survey respondents (almost half completed a university degree) probably reflect both, the high education levels of Syrian refugees in Europe and an already observed bias of online surveys towards more highly educated individuals (Pötzschke, Ersanilli (workshop presentations Krems, September 2022)). A deeper look into of the data supports the idea that survey breakoffs were related to educational levels and gender: Respondents with higher education levels were significantly more likely to complete the survey than those with lower education levels. Respondents who identified as women were significantly less likely than those who identified as men to complete the survey.

Chapter 2.3. Data cleaning

In the cleaning process, we first changed label and variable names and corrected the category type for some variables (sometimes categorical variables were set as string variables by LimeSurvey). We also converted Arabic-number style to Western-number style.

We also corrected missing values for multiple-choice questions. The export settings in LimeSurvey have to be set to 0 for unticked responses prior to data export; otherwise LimeSurvey exports unticked responses as missing values and merges them with truly missing values, which makes the analysis and interpretation of unticked options impossible. We also double-checked the filter questions for the target population. We also created a variable for survey duration. As assumed, the overall mean for survey duration was 15,4 minutes (with a large standard deviation of 29 minutes). The median was 9,2 minutes.

In the data cleaning process, the original dataset of 4,876 observations was reduced to 4,706 observations due to discovered duplicates. We detected duplicates based on IP addresses and contact details.

We discovered duplicates in IP addresses, email addresses and phone numbers. We found 197 duplicated IP addresses (around 4% of the sample). For 146 responses, the IP address was missing; for them, it was impossible to check for duplicates. This could be linked to respondent behaviour; if respondents used VPNs, proxies, or privacy tools, LimeSurvey might not capture a usable IP. It is not entirely clear what drives repeated responses; the survey ad and participant information did not mention a financial compensation. There were many duplicated cases where one observation had very uncomplete answers, while a later duplicate was filled out until the end. We assume that these might be respondents who looked at the survey but did not have time to fill it out at that moment and came back to it later. There were also other cases where four surveys were filled out completely at the same IP address at different points in time, with reasonable survey duration and different contact details. Given the relative length of the survey (15-20min), we suspect that these might be respondents who share the same router, either in a shared flat or a reception centre. In most home or office networks, multiple devices share a single public IP address assigned by the Internet Service Provider, which means that everyone behind the same router appears to have the same public IP address to external websites.

We mostly followed Ersanili (2020) in how we dealt with duplicates in IP address: Overall, we retained the most complete copy. In case of two or more equally complete copies, the first copy was retained. If two or more copies were filled out until the end, we retained them if they had different answers, different contact addresses and different dates and respondents used a legitimate time to fill out the survey, assuming that respondents might share the same router. Considering the length of the SYREALITY survey, it is unlikely that respondents would fill out the complete survey several times with different answers and invent different contact details. This is overall in line with what other studies collecting data through Facebook have done (Rosenzweig et al, 2020; Iannelli et al, 2020). Overall, we dropped 164 observations based on IP duplication.

We also detected 5 duplicates based on email addresses. We kept the most complete copy; if filled out to an identical degree, we kept the first copy. We also detected one duplicate based on phone number (with a different IP addresses) with both versions being completed. We kept the first copy.

We also checked for extreme values (speeding) in survey duration. We checked for suspiciously short survey duration (shorter than the median – 8 min) if the survey was completed. However, we did not find any cases of excessive speeding. We checked observations of full responses for streamlining if they completed the survey in under 10 minutes but responses looked legitimate. There were some observations with very long survey duration. We assume that these might be related to interruptions during filling out the survey as the settings in LimeSurvey were set to allowing to save and continue later.

We also added a variable differentiating four response categories:

1) Opened survey but did not answer any questions (if E1 was missing);

- 2) Opened survey but not part of target group (determined based on replies to filter questions: either not born in Syria (E1), nor having Syrian citizenship (or don't know) (E2); not born between 1957 and 1996 (E3), not left Syria after 2011 (E4); not living in either Greece, Austria, Germany or Netherlands (E5);
- 3) Part of target group, answered several questions but did not complete survey until the end (questions before SAT4)
- 4) Part of target group and completed survey (measured as answering questions from SAT4 and onwards)

This variable helped us to better understand breakoffs: 3,3% opened the survey without any question; 15,0% opened the survey but were not part of the target population, 40,3% were part of the target population and completed the survey partly and 41,4% were part of the target population and completed the survey. This means that the break-off rate of eligible survey participants was 49,3%.

To anonymize the data, we created a separate contact database excel sheet which stores the personal identifiers (email address, phone number, Facebook account name) together with a unique participant ID and the respondents' current country of living. Subsequently we deleted all IP addresses, phone numbers, email addresses, and Facebook account names to anonymise the dataset.

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Annex

Annex 1: Survey questionnaire English [17 January 2023]

The SYREALITY Survey

University for
Continuing
Education Krems

Welcome.

You are invited to participate in a survey on **life wishes** of **Syrians** who live in **Austria, Germany, the Netherlands and Greece** to understand what people think and feel about their lives and the challenges they face.

The survey is part of a research project led by Dr Lea Müller-Funk based at the **University for Continuing Education Krems, Austria**. The project is not connected to any governmental authorities. Your participation may help NGOs and policymakers to base their decisions on the evidence we collect.

The University for Continuing Education Krems guarantees that your information will remain confidential and will be stored on a secure server. For more information click [here](#).

You can fill out the questionnaire in Arabic or English. It will take no longer than 20 minutes to complete. **Please note: You must be born between 1957 and 1996 to participate.**

By completing this survey, you are consenting to participate in our study.
Thank you for your help and cooperation.

This survey is anonymous.

The record of your survey responses does not contain any identifying information about you, unless a specific survey question explicitly asked for it.

If you used an identifying access code to access this survey, please rest assured that this code will not be stored together with your responses. It is managed in a separate database and will only be updated to indicate whether you did (or did not) complete this survey. There is no way of matching identification access codes with survey responses.

To continue please first accept our survey privacy policy.

[Show policy](#)

Privacy Notice for Research Project SYREALITY

Controller (Art 4/7 GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation))

University for Continuing Studies Krems (Danube-University Krems)

Department for Migration and Globalisation

Dr.-Karl-Dorrek-Straße 30, 3500 Krems an der Donau

Contact person: Dr. Lea Müller-Funk (lea.mueller-funk@donau-uni.ac.at)

Data Protection Officer: Dr. Daniel Stanonik and Dr. Karsten Kinast (datenschutz@donau-uni.ac.at)

Purpose of Processing

Collection of information in the context of the above-mentioned research project.

We provide the following online questionnaire via the portal of LimeSurvey GmbH, Papenreya 63, 22453 Hamburg (Germany) with whom we have concluded a processing agreement. By accessing the survey website, LimeSurvey receives log information, i.e. cookies that are necessary for the technical processing (caching etc.) of the survey. Through the questionnaire you provide us with information about demographic information, your displacement trajectory, life plans, migration and stay aspirations, questions related to work, poverty and wealth, as well as life satisfaction and hope, which, even in relation to each other, do not allow us to draw any conclusions about your specific identity.

Legal Basis

Art. 89 in conjunction with Art. 6 (1) lit e GDPR in conjunction with § 3 Z 1, 7 and 8 of the Austrian University Act (UG) [= development of science (research and teaching); support of national and international cooperation in the field of scientific research; use and implementation of research results in practice].

Recipients

Targeted participants in the survey are people born in Syria who left Syria after 2011 who are currently living in Austria, Germany, Netherlands, or Greece and are aged 27-65. A transfer of your personal data to third parties does not take place.

Storage Period

Log information is stored for the duration of the session. The data of the online survey can be archived indefinitely due to the lack of identifiability of the individual participants.

Your Rights

To exercise the rights to information, erasure etc. in accordance with Art. 15 - 20 GDPR, please contact the contact person indicated above or, subsidiarily, the data protection officer. Due to lack of identifiability, your rights may be limited without providing further information according to 11 GDPR. You may lodge your eventual complaints with the Austrian supervisory authority at www.dsb.gv.at.

Eligibility (E)

We would first like to ask you some questions about your personal situation.

E1 Were you born in Syria?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)

E2 Do you currently have Syrian citizenship?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- Don't know (97)

If E1 == 0 & E2 == 1 or

If E1 == 1 & E2 == 0 or

If E1 == 1 & E2 == 1

E3 In which year were you born?

- 1957
- 1958
- 1959
- 1960
- 1961
- 1962
- 1963
- 1964
- 1965
- 1966
- 1967
- 1968
- 1969
- 1970
- 1971
- 1972
- 1973
- 1974
- 1975
- 1976
- 1977
- 1978
- 1979
- 1980
- 1981

- 1982
- 1983
- 1984
- 1985
- 1986
- 1987
- 1988
- 1989
- 1990
- 1991
- 1992
- 1993
- 1994
- 1995
- 1996
- Other (999)

If E3 == 1957-1996

E4 Did you leave Syria for the last time after 2011?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)

If E4 == 1

E5 Are you currently living in either...

- Austria (1)
- Germany (2)
- The Netherlands (3)
- Greece (4), or
- Other (5)

If E5 == 1, 2, 3 or 4

E6 Since which year have you lived in [Austria/Germany/The Netherlands/Greece]?

- 2011
- 2012
- 2013
- 2014
- 2015
- 2016
- 2017
- 2018
- 2019
- 2020

- 2021
- 2022
- 2023 (drop-down)

If E1 == 0 & E2 == 0 OR

If E1 == 0 & E2 == 97 OR

If E3 == 999 OR

If E4 == 0 OR

If E5 == 5

END5 Unfortunately you are not eligible to participate in this survey. We are only interviewing Syrians in Austria, Germany, the Netherlands, and Greece born between 1957 and 1996 who left Syria after 2011.

Demographics 1 (DEM1)

DEM1 Please tell me, are you...

- A man (1)
- A woman (2)
- Other (3)

DEM2 What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- No formal education (1)
- Primary school (grade 1-6) (2)
- Middle School (grade 7-9) (3)
- Secondary School general (grade 10-12) (4)
- Secondary School in arts, industry or commerce (grade 10-12) (5)
- Post-secondary (technical certificate) (6)
- University BA (7)
- University MA (8)
- University PhD (9)

DEM3 What is your marital status?

- Single (1)
- Married or in a long-term relationship (2)
- Divorced or widowed (3)
- Don't know (97)

DEM4 Do you currently have children?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)

Life aspirations in the past and present (ASP)

In the following questions, we would like to hear about your wishes and plans for your life in the past and now.

ASP1 First, we would like to know what you think was the most important event in your life in the last 15 years? This can refer to a life-changing event or a stressful event, such as the death of a spouse, divorce, the birth of a child, a career change, or a change of place of residence.

ASP2 Now we are going to talk about your wishes related to education. Have you ever strongly wished to pursue or continue your education?

This can be school, university, workshops, or vocational training.

- Yes (1)
- No (0)

If ASP2 == 1

ASP3 When did you have this wish related to education?

Check all that apply.

- Before 2011 (1)
- Between 2011 and my arrival in Europe (2)
- Between my arrival in Europe and now (3)

ASP4 Was your school or university education in Syria interrupted because of the war?

- No, it wasn't interrupted. (1)
- Yes, and I couldn't continue my education. (2)
- Yes, but I could continue my education before I came to Europe. (3)
- Yes, but I could continue my education in Europe. (4)
- I was not involved in any study in this time. (5).

ASP00 Now we are going to talk about your wishes related to family and relationships in three periods – in 2010, between 2011 and your arrival in Europe and since then.

ASP5a In 2010, did you strongly wish to...?

Check all that apply.

- Get married and start a family; (1)
- Live in the same house with your parents / partner / children; (2)
- Have a different romantic relationship than your family accepts; (3)
- End a relationship or get a divorce; (4)
- Improve your romantic relationship; (5)
- Other, please specify _____ (6)
- No, I had no strong wishes related to family and relationships. (7)

ASP5b Between 2011 and your arrival in Europe, did you strongly wish to...?

Check all that apply.

- Get married and start a family; (1)
- Live in the same house with your parents / partner / children; (2)
- Have a different romantic relationship than your family accepts; (3)
- End a relationship or get a divorce; (4)
- Improve your romantic relationship? (5)
- Other, please specify_____ (6)
- No, I had no wishes related to family and relationships. (7)

ASP5c Between your arrival in Europe and now, have you strongly wished to...?

Check all that apply.

- Get married and start a family; (1)
- Live in the same house with your parents / partner / children; (2)
- Have a different romantic relationship than your family accepts; (3)
- End a relationship or get a divorce; (4)
- Improve your romantic relationship? (5)
- Other, please specify_____ (6)
- No, I have had no wishes related to family and relationships. (7)

ASP6a Now we are going to talk about your wishes related to work in three periods – in 2010, between 2011 and your arrival in Europe, and since then.

In 2010, did you strongly wish to pursue a specific professional career in your life?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)

If ASP6a == 1

ASP6b In 2010, which profession did you wish to pursue?

Please choose the category you feel fits you best.

- Higher administrator (for example: banker, executive in big business, high government official, union official, high army officers (e.g. major) (2)
- Professional and technical (for example: doctor, teacher, engineer, artist, accountant, nurse, non-commissioned officers in army (e.g. lieutenant) (1)
- Clerical (for example: secretary, clerk, office manager, civil servant, bookkeeper) (3)
- Sales (for example: sales manager, shop owner, shop assistant, insurance agent, buyer) (4)
- Service (for example: restaurant owner, police officer, waiter, barber, caretaker, soldier) (5)
- Skilled worker (for example: foreman, motor mechanic, printer, seamstress, tool and die maker, electrician) (6)
- Semi-skilled worker (for example: bricklayer, bus driver, tannery worker, carpenter, sheet metal worker, baker) (7)
- Unskilled worker (for example: labourer, porter, unskilled factory worker, cleaner) (8)

- Farm worker (for example: farm labourer, tractor driver) (9)
- Farm proprietor, farm manager (10)

ASP6c Between 2011 and your arrival in Europe, did you strongly wish to pursue a specific professional career in your life?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)

If ASP6c == 1

ASP6d Between 2011 and your arrival in Europe, which profession did you wish to pursue?

Please choose the category you feel fits you best.

- Higher administrator (for example: banker, executive in big business, high government official, union official, high army officers (e.g. major) (2)
- Professional and technical (for example: doctor, teacher, engineer, artist, accountant, nurse, non-commissioned officers in army (e.g lieutenant) (1)
- Sales (for example: sales manager, shop owner, shop assistant, insurance agent, buyer) (4)
- Clerical (for example: secretary, clerk, office manager, civil servant, bookkeeper) (3)
- Service (for example: restaurant owner, police officer, waiter, barber, caretaker, soldier) (5)
- Skilled worker (for example: foreman, motor mechanic, printer, seamstress, tool and die maker, electrician) (6)
- Semi-skilled worker (for example: bricklayer, bus driver, tannery worker, carpenter, sheet metal worker, baker) (7)
- Unskilled worker (for example: labourer, porter, unskilled factory worker, cleaner) (8)
- Farm worker (for example: farm labourer, tractor driver) (9)
- Farm proprietor, farm manager (10)

ASP6e Between your arrival in Europe and now, have you strongly wished to pursue a specific professional career in your life?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)

If ASP6e == 1

ASP6f Between your arrival in Europe and now, which profession have you wished to pursue?

Please choose the category you feel fits you best.

- Higher administrator (for example: banker, executive in big business, high government official, union official, high army officers (e.g. major) (2)
- Professional and technical (for example: doctor, teacher, engineer, artist, accountant, nurse, non-commissioned officers in army (e.g lieutenant) (1)
- Sales (for example: sales manager, shop owner, shop assistant, insurance agent, buyer) (4)
- Clerical (for example: secretary, clerk, office manager, civil servant, bookkeeper) (3)
- Service (for example: restaurant owner, police officer, waiter, barber, caretaker, soldier) (5)

- Skilled worker (for example: foreman, motor mechanic, printer, seamstress, tool and die maker, electrician) (6)
- Semi-skilled worker (for example: bricklayer, bus driver, tannery worker, carpenter, sheet metal worker, baker) (7)
- Unskilled worker (for example: labourer, porter, unskilled factory worker, cleaner) (8)
- Farm worker (for example: farm labourer, tractor driver) (9)
- Farm proprietor, farm manager (10)

ASP7 Now we are going to talk about social and political change. Have you ever strongly wished to change social traditions and/or politics in Syria?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)

If ASP7 == 1

ASP8 When was that?

Check all that apply.

- Before 2011 (1)
- Between 2011 and my arrival in Europe (2)
- Between my arrival in Europe and now (3)

If ASP7 == 1

ASP9 Have you personally ever actively done something to change social traditions and/or politics in Syria, whether in private life or in public?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- Prefer not to say (98)

If ASP9 == 1

ASP10 There are many things people can do to make social and political change happen. Have you done any of the following?

Check all that apply.

- Participated in local groups or youth initiatives (1)
- Participated in a civil society organisation (2)
- Tried to change some social norms and tradition in my own private life (3)
- Voiced my political opinion publicly (media, protests, advocacy campaign etc) (4)
- Joined a political party (5)
- Participated in a political movement other than a party (6)
- Joined armed group (7)
- Created support networks among like-minded individuals (8)
- Other, please specify _____ (9)
- Prefer not to say (98)

ASP11 How interested would you say you are in politics nowadays – are you...?

- Very interested (1)
- Quite interested (2)
- Hardly interested (3)
- Not at all interested (4)
- Prefer not to say (98)

ASP12 Do you follow the political events in Syria?

- Yes, to some extent (1)
- No, not at all (2)

ASP13 Do you follow the political events in [Austria/Germany/Greece/The Netherlands]?

- Yes, to some extent (1)
- No, not at all (2)

If ASP9 == 1:

FEMACT1 Have you personally ever actively done something for the equality between men and women in Syria, whether in private life or in public?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- Prefer not to say (98)

If FEMACT1 ==1

FEMACT2 When was that?

Check all that apply.

- Before 2011 (1)
- Between 2011 and my arrival in Europe (2)
- Between my arrival in Europe and now (3)

If FEMACT1 ==1

FEMACT3 What inspired you to actively do something for the equality between men and women?

Check all that apply.

- I saw that women were treated unfairly compared to men in my community, in Syria or abroad. (1)
- I personally experienced discrimination and/or violence in Syria because I am a woman. (2)
- I personally experienced discrimination and/or violence abroad because I am a woman. (3)
- I received a training about women's rights in Syria. (4)
- I received a training about women's rights abroad. (5)
- I read book/s about feminism and women issues. (6)
- I worked for a feminist organization inside Syria. (7)
- I work(ed) for a feminist organization outside of Syria. (8)
- I know an inspiring feminist person like a friend or a family member. (9)
- Other please specify _____ (10)

If FEMACT1 ==1

FEMACT4 Do you identify as a feminist?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)

Displacement trajectory (D)

Thank you for your answers so far. The next section is about where you lived before 2011 and since then.

D1 At the end of 2010, in which province in Syria did you live?

- Aleppo Governorate (1)
- Damascus Governorate (2)
- Daraa Governorate (3)
- Deir ez-Zor Governorate (4)
- Hama Governorate (5)
- Al-Hasakah Governorate (6)
- Homs Governorate (7)
- Idlib Governorate (8)
- Latakia Governorate (9)
- Quneitra Governorate (10)
- Raqqa Governorate (11)
- Rif Dimashq Governorate (12)
- As-Suwayda Governorate (13)
- Tartus Governorate (14)

D2 At the end of 2010, did you live in either...

- The countryside (1), or
- A city (2)

D3 After 2011, were you displaced inside Syria?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)

D4 After 2011, under which political control did you live the longest in Syria?

- Regime (1)
- Opposition (2)
- ISIS (3)
- Autonomous Administration of North and East Syria (4)
- Other, please specify _____ (5)
- I did not live in Syria after March 2011. (6)
- Don't know (97)

- Prefer not to say (98)

If D3 == 1

D5 After 2011, were you obliged to move to a region under different political control in Syria?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- Prefer not to say (98)

D6 I could not stay in Syria anymore because...

You can choose several options.

- I had or was afraid of a threat targeting me in person. (1)
- I was afraid of bombings. (2)
- I was deprived from freedom of expression. (3)
- I did not want to fight for any party / a particular party. (4)
- Of the bad economic situation. (5)
- I had no place to stay after my house was destroyed. (6)
- I wanted to join a family member abroad. (7)
- I couldn't access education. (8)
- I couldn't access health services. (9)
- Other reason, please specify: _____ (10)
- Prefer not to say (98)

D7a After 2011, did you live in another country / countries apart from Syria and [Austria/Germany/The Netherlands/Greece] for one year or more?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)

If D7a == 1

D7b In which country / countries did you live for one year or more after 2011?

Check all that apply.

- Turkey (1)
- Jordan (2)
- Lebanon (3)
- Egypt (4)
- Saudi Arabia (5)
- United Arab Emirates (6)
- Greece (7)
- Italy (8)
- Hungary (9)
- Austria (10)
- Germany (11)
- Netherlands (12)

- Sweden (13)
- Other, please specify _____ (14)
- Prefer not to say (98)

D8 Do you currently live in either...

- The countryside (1),
- A city (not the capital) (2), or
- The capital city) (3)

D9 What is your current legal status in this country?

- Refugee status or temporary protection (1)
- Asylum-seeker (still under procedure) (2)
- My asylum application was rejected in this country. (3)
- Residence permit as student (4)
- Residence permit for work (5)
- I have citizenship in this country. (6)
- I did not apply for any residence in this country. (7)
- Other, please specify _____ (8)
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

If D9 = 1, 4, 5

D10 In which year were you granted asylum/residency?

- 2011
- 2012
- 2013
- 2014
- 2015
- 2016
- 2017
- 2018
- 2019
- 2020
- 2021
- 2022
- 2023 (drop-down)
- Don't know (97)

D11 How often do you communicate with family and/or friends in Syria? (call, chat, email, visit)

- Around once a week (1)
- Around once a month (2)
- Around once every few months (3)

- Around once a year (4)
- Less than once a year (5)
- Never (6)
- I don't have any family members or friends in Syria. (7)
- Prefer not to say (98)

D12 How frequently do you use social media such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Telegram or Signal?

This can be for communication and/or leisure.

- Daily (1)
- Several times a week (2)
- Once a week (3)
- Less than once a week (4)
- Never (5)

D13 Since your arrival in Europe, are you (or your partner) financially responsible for any family member outside of the European Union?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- Prefer not to say (98)

Asylum Policies (POL)

POL1 Now we are interested in your thoughts about how life is here in Europe. Do you think that life for Syrians in Europe is overall...?

- Very bad (1)
- Bad (2)
- Neither good nor bad (3)
- Good (4)
- Very good (5)
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

POL2 Do you think that the help from the government in [Germany/Austria/the Netherlands/Greece] for Syrians, who are in need and live here, is...?

- Very bad (1)
- Bad (2)
- Neither good nor bad (3)
- Good (4), or
- Very good (5)
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

Migration and stay aspirations, now and in the future (MIG)

Now, we would like to ask you some questions about living outside Syria and your thoughts about living in another country.

If D7a == 1

MIG1 Since you left Syria until you arrived here, have you ever wanted to stay in a country in which you lived but you couldn't stay?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

If D7a == 1 & MIG1 == 1

MIG2 In which country / countries?

Check all that apply.

- Turkey (1)
- Jordan (2)
- Lebanon (3)
- Egypt (4)
- Saudi Arabia (5)
- United Arab Emirates (6)
- Greece (7)
- Italy (8)
- Hungary (9)
- Austria (10)
- Germany (11)
- Netherlands (12)
- Sweden (13)
- Other, please specify _____ (14)

MIG3 Before you came to live in [Austria / Germany / The Netherlands / Greece], were any of your nuclear family – this means your partner/spouse, your parents or your children – already living here?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)

MIG4 Would you like to go and live in another country sometime during the next five years, or would you prefer to stay in [Austria / Germany / The Netherlands / Greece]?

- Go (1)
- Stay (2)
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

If MIG4 == 1

MIG5 Which country would you like to go to?

- Ethiopia 1
- Azerbaijan 2
- Jordan 3
- Armenia 4
- Spain 5
- Australia 6
- Estonia 7
- Afghanistan 8
- Albania 9
- Germany 10
- United Arab Emirates 11
- Indonesia 12
- Ukraine 13
- Iran 14
- Ireland 15
- Iceland 16
- Italy 17
- Pakistan 18
- Bahrain 19
- Portugal 20
- Brunei 21
- Belgium 22
- Bulgaria 23
- Bosnia and Herzegovina 24
- Poland 25
- Belarus 26
- Turkmenistan 27
- Tunisia 28
- Montenegro 29
- Algeria 30
- Czech Republic 31
- South Africa 32
- South Sudan 33
- Georgia 34
- Djibouti 35
- Denmark 36
- State of Qatar 37
- Turkey 38
- Russia 39

- Romania 40
- Oman 41
- Slovakia 42
- Slovenia 43
- Singapore 44
- Sweden 45
- Switzerland 46
- Serbia 47
- Iraq 48
- France 49
- Palestine 50
- Finland 51
- Philippines 52
- Cyprus 53
- Croatia 54
- Canada 55
- Kosovo 56
- Kuwait 57
- Latvia 58
- Lebanon 59
- Luxembourg 60
- Libya 61
- Lithuania 62
- Liechtenstein 63
- Malta 64
- Malaysia 65
- Egypt 66
- Morocco 67
- Macedonia 68
- Saudi Arabia 69
- United Kingdom 70
- Mauritania 71
- Moldova 72
- Monaco 73
- Norway 74
- Austria 75
- New Zealand 76
- India 77
- Hungary 78
- The Netherlands 79
- United States of America 80
- Yemen 81

- Greece 82
- Other, please specify _____
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

MIG6 Since you arrived in this country, have you ever prepared to move to another country, but not been able to go?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- Prefer not to say (98)

MIG7 Would you like to change your current place of stay in [Austria / Germany / The Netherlands / Greece]?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

MIG8 Would you like to return to live in Syria in the next 5 years?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

MIG9 Some Syrians considered to return to Syria for different reasons. Have you ever considered to return but not been able to go?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- Prefer not to say (98)

MIG10 Would you like to return to live in Syria at some point in the future in case it is safe?

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

If MIG10 == 1

MIG11 What do you wish to happen in Syria to say that it is safe to return to?

No mandatory question, option "no answer"

Demographics 2 (DEM)

We would now like to ask you some more questions about your personal situation.

If DEM3 == 2

DEM5 Where does your spouse/partner currently live?

- In the same household as me (1)
- In the same country as me, but not with me (2)
- In another country (3)
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

If DEM4 == 1

DEM6 Do your children currently live with you in [Austria/Germany/Netherlands/Greece]?

- Yes, all (1)
- Yes, some (2)
- No, none (3)
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

DEM7 What is your religion?

- Prefer not to say (98)
- Muslim Sunni (1)
- Muslim Shia (2)
- Muslim Alawi (3)
- Other Muslim (4)
- Druze (5)
- Yazidi (6)
- Christian (7)
- Jewish (8)
- No religion (atheist) (9)
- Other, please specify _____ (10)
- Don't know (97)

DEM8 When you were a child, what language did you speak at home with your parents?

Check all that apply.

- Arabic (1)
- Kurdish (2)
- Turkish (3)
- Armenian (4)
- Other, please specify _____ (5)

DEM9 In which other languages are you able to have a conversation about everyday life?

Check all that apply.

- Arabic (1)
- Kurdish (2)
- Turkish (3)
- Armenian (4)
- English (5)
- French (6)
- German (7)
- Dutch (8)
- Greek (9)
- Other, please specify _____ (10)
- I don't speak another language (11)

Work, poverty and wealth (WPW)

WPW1 Now we would like to know more about your work experience and your economic situation.

Have you ever done any paid work? This includes being self-employed.

- Yes (1)
- No (0)

If WPW1 == 1

WPW2 What best describes your longest paid job?

Please choose the category you feel fits you best.

- Higher administrator (for example: banker, executive in big business, high government official, union official, high army officers (e.g. major) (2)
- Professional and technical (for example: doctor, teacher, engineer, artist, accountant, nurse, non-commissioned officers in army (e.g. lieutenant) (1)
- Sales (for example: sales manager, shop owner, shop assistant, insurance agent, buyer) (4)
- Clerical (for example: secretary, clerk, office manager, civil servant, bookkeeper) (3)
- Service (for example: restaurant owner, police officer, waiter, barber, caretaker, soldier) (5)
- Skilled worker (for example: foreman, motor mechanic, printer, seamstress, tool and die maker, electrician) (6)
- Semi-skilled worker (for example: bricklayer, bus driver, tannery worker, carpenter, sheet metal worker, baker) (7)
- Unskilled worker (for example: labourer, porter, unskilled factory worker, cleaner) (8)
- Farm worker (for example: farm labourer, tractor driver) (9)
- Farm proprietor, farm manager (10)

If WPW1 == 1

WPW3 Was this job also your main job before 2011?

- Yes (1)

- No (0)

If WPW3 == 0

WPW4 What best describes your main paid job before 2011?

Please choose the category you feel fits you best.

- Professional and technical (for example: doctor, teacher, engineer, artist, accountant, nurse, non-commissioned officers in army (e.g lieutenant) (1)
- Higher administrator (for example: banker, executive in big business, high government official, union official, high army officers (e.g. major) (2)
- Clerical (for example: secretary, clerk, office manager, civil servant, bookkeeper) (3)
- Sales (for example: sales manager, shop owner, shop assistant, insurance agent, buyer) (4)
- Service (for example: restaurant owner, police officer, waiter, barber, caretaker, soldier) (5)
- Skilled worker (for example: foreman, motor mechanic, printer, seamstress, tool and die maker, electrician) (6)
- Semi-skilled worker (for example: bricklayer, bus driver, tannery worker, carpenter, sheet metal worker, baker) (7)
- Unskilled worker (for example: labourer, porter, unskilled factory worker, cleaner) (8)
- Farm worker (for example: farm labourer, tractor driver) (9)
- Farm proprietor, farm manager (10)
- I did not have a job before 2011 (11)

If WPW1 == 1 & D7 == 1

WPW5 Now I would like you to think about the entire time since you left Syria until you came to [\[Austria/Germany/The Netherlands/Greece\]](#). What best describes your longest job for this time period?

Please choose the category you feel fits you best.

- I did not have a job in this period (11)
- Higher administrator (for example: banker, executive in big business, high government official, union official, high army officers (e.g. major) (2)
- Professional and technical (for example: doctor, teacher, engineer, artist, accountant, nurse, non-commissioned officers in army (e.g lieutenant) (1)
- Sales (for example: sales manager, shop owner, shop assistant, insurance agent, buyer) (4)
- Clerical (for example: secretary, clerk, office manager, civil servant, bookkeeper) (3)
- Service (for example: restaurant owner, police officer, waiter, barber, caretaker, soldier) (5)
- Skilled worker (for example: foreman, motor mechanic, printer, seamstress, tool and die maker, electrician) (6)
- Semi-skilled worker (for example: bricklayer, bus driver, tannery worker, carpenter, sheet metal worker, baker) (7)
- Unskilled worker (for example: labourer, porter, unskilled factory worker, cleaner) (8)
- Farm worker (for example: farm labourer, tractor driver) (9)
- Farm proprietor, farm manager (10)

If WPW1 == 1

WPW6 Now we will talk about your current work. What describes your current situation in [Austria/Germany/The Netherlands/Greece] best?

- I am in full-time employment (1)
- I am in part-time employment (2)
- I am in minimal or irregular employment (3)
- I am doing professional training or an internship (4)
- I am temporarily out of work (5)
- I am responsible for caring for family members, shopping and housework (6)
- I am retired/pensioner (7)
- I am a student (school, high school, university, language) (8)

If WPW6 == 1, 2, or 3

WPW7 What best describes your present job in [Austria/Germany/The Netherlands/Greece]?

Please choose the category you feel fits you best.

- Higher administrator (for example: banker, executive in big business, high government official, union official, high army officers (e.g. major) (2)
- Professional and technical (for example: doctor, teacher, engineer, artist, accountant, nurse, non-commissioned officers in army (e.g lieutenant) (1)
- Clerical (for example: secretary, clerk, office manager, civil servant, bookkeeper) (3)
- Sales (for example: sales manager, shop owner, shop assistant, insurance agent, buyer) (4)
- Service (for example: restaurant owner, police officer, waiter, barber, caretaker, soldier) (5)
- Skilled worker (for example: foreman, motor mechanic, printer, seamstress, tool and die maker, electrician) (6)
- Semi-skilled worker (for example: bricklayer, bus driver, tannery worker, carpenter, sheet metal worker, baker) (7)
- Unskilled worker (for example: labourer, porter, unskilled factory worker, cleaner) (8)
- Farm worker (for example: farm labourer, tractor driver) (9)
- Farm proprietor, farm manager (10)

If WPW1 == 0 & DEM3 == 2

WPW8 Has your spouse/partner ever done any paid work? This includes being self-employed.

- Yes (1)
- No (0)

If WPW1 == 0 & DEM3 == 2 & WPW8 == 1

WPW9 What best describes his/her longest paid job?

Please choose the category you feel fits best.

- Higher administrator (for example: banker, executive in big business, high government official, union official, high army officers (e.g. major) (2)
- Professional and technical (for example: doctor, teacher, engineer, artist, accountant, nurse, non-commissioned officers in army (e.g lieutenant) (1)
- Sales (for example: sales manager, shop owner, shop assistant, insurance agent, buyer) (4)
- Clerical (for example: secretary, clerk, office manager, civil servant, bookkeeper) (3)

- Service (for example: restaurant owner, police officer, waiter, barber, caretaker, soldier) (5)
- Skilled worker (for example: foreman, motor mechanic, printer, seamstress, tool and die maker, electrician) (6)
- Semi-skilled worker (for example: bricklayer, bus driver, tannery worker, carpenter, sheet metal worker, baker) (7)
- Unskilled worker (for example: labourer, porter, unskilled factory worker, cleaner) (8)
- Farm worker (for example: farm labourer, tractor driver) (9)
- Farm proprietor, farm manager (10)

If WPW1 == 0 & DEM3 == 1, 3, or 97 OR

If WPW1 == 0 & DEM3 == 2 & WPW8 == 0

WPW10 When you were 14, was your father...

- Working as an employee (1),
- Self-employed, owned business or farm (2),
- Not working (3)
- Dead/absent? (4)
- Don't know (97)

If WPW10 == 1, 2

WPW11 When you were 14, what best describes your father's job?

Please choose the category you feel fits best.

- Higher administrator (for example: banker, executive in big business, high government official, union official, high army officers (e.g. major) (2)
- Professional and technical (for example: doctor, teacher, engineer, artist, accountant, nurse, non-commissioned officers in army (e.g lieutenant) (1)
- Sales (for example: sales manager, shop owner, shop assistant, insurance agent, buyer) (4)
- Clerical (for example: secretary, clerk, office manager, civil servant, bookkeeper) (3)
- Service (for example: restaurant owner, police officer, waiter, barber, caretaker, soldier) (5)
- Skilled worker (for example: foreman, motor mechanic, printer, seamstress, tool and die maker, electrician) (6)
- Semi-skilled worker (for example: bricklayer, bus driver, tannery worker, carpenter, sheet metal worker, baker) (7)
- Unskilled worker (for example: labourer, porter, unskilled factory worker, cleaner) (8)
- Farm worker (for example: farm labourer, tractor driver) (9)
- Farm proprietor, farm manager (10)
- Don't know (97)

WPW12 In 2010, which of the following statements best describes your financial situation?

- We mostly did not have enough money even for food (1)
- We had enough money but only for the most necessary things (2)
- Usually, we had enough money, but we had to borrow/save to buy expensive things, such as a refrigerator and a TV (3)
- We could afford expensive purchases without too much difficulty, but buying a car was difficult (4)

- We could buy a car without much effort, but buying a home was beyond our means (5)
- We could afford anything we wanted (6)
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

WPW13 In 2010, did you or your family own property (house, business, or land)?

Check all that apply.

- Yes, one house or more (1)
- Yes, one business or more (2)
- Yes, land (3)
- No, we didn't own anything of the above (4)
- Don't know (97)

No mandatory question, option "no answer"

WPW14 After 2011, has your personal property been looted, confiscated, or destroyed?

- Yes, all of them (1)
- Yes, some of them (2)
- No (0)
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

If WPW13 == 1,2,or 3

WPW15 After 2011, did you lose any documentation over your property?

- Yes, all of them (1)
- Yes, some of them (2)
- No (0)
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

WPW16 Which of the following statements best describes your financial situation in the moment when you left Syria?

- We mostly did not have enough money even for food (1)
- We had enough money but only for the most necessary things (2)
- Usually, we had enough money, but to buy expensive things, such as a refrigerator, a TV and a washing machine, we had to save or borrow money (3)
- We could afford expensive purchases without too much difficulty, but buying a car was difficult (4)
- We could buy a car without much effort, but buying a home was beyond our means (5)
- We could afford anything we wanted (6)
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

WPW17 Since your arrival in [Austria/Germany/the Netherlands/Greece] until now, how has your financial situation changed?

- Has significantly improved (1)
- Has somewhat improved (2)
- Remains unchanged (3)
- Has deteriorated somewhat (4)
- Is much worse (5)
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

WPW18 Look at the image. Think of this ladder as representing where people stood in Syrian society before 2011. At the top of the ladder are the people who have the most money, most education, and best jobs. At the bottom are the people who have the least money, least education, and worst jobs or no job. Please choose the position on the rung that best represents where you think you stood on the ladder.

- top of the ladder
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
- bottom of the ladder
- Prefer not to say (98)

WPW19 Look at the image again and think about the moment when you left Syria. Please choose the position on the rung that best represents where you think you stood on the ladder.

- top of the ladder
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
- bottom of the ladder
- Prefer not to say (98)

WPW20 Look at the image again and think about the society here in [Austria/Germany/The Netherlands, Greece] and your position today. Please choose the position on the rung that best represents where you think you stand on the ladder.

- top of the ladder
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
- bottom of the ladder
- Prefer not to say (98)

Life satisfaction and hope (SAT)

SAT1a You are almost done. Before we finish, we would like to know more about how you feel about your life these days.

In general, how are things going in your life nowadays?

10 indicates excellent and 1 very bad.

- 10 excellent
- 9
- 8
- 7
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3

- 2
- 1 very bad
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

SAT1b How satisfied are you overall with your life these days?

10 indicates the highest satisfaction and 1 the lowest.

- 10 highest level of satisfaction
- 9
- 8
- 7
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 lowest level of satisfaction
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

SAT2 How satisfied are you currently with your mental well-being these days?

10 indicates the highest satisfaction and 1 the lowest.

- 10 highest level of satisfaction
- 9
- 8
- 7
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 lowest level of satisfaction
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

SAT3 How hopeful are you about your future in Europe these days?

10 indicates the highest amount of hope and 1 the lowest.

- 10 highest amount of hope
- 9
- 8
- 7
- 6

- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 lowest amount of hope
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

SAT4 How hopeful are you about the future of Syria these days?

10 indicates the highest amount of hope and 1 the lowest.

- 10 highest amount of hope
- 9
- 8
- 7
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 lowest amount of hope
- Don't know (97)
- Prefer not to say (98)

SAT5 What do you do to feel good these days?

No mandatory question, option "no answer"

END1 We have reached the end of the survey. What was your overall impression of this survey?

END2 Thank you for taking the time to answer our questions! We would like to send you another, shorter survey, some years from now to see how you are doing. Would you be willing to participate?

- Yes, I might be willing (1)
- No, I definitely don't want to participate again (0)

If D8 == 3

END3 There is also the opportunity to tell us more about your experiences in a longer personal conversation in Arabic. Would you be willing to participate?

- Yes, I might be willing (1)
- No, I definitely don't want to participate again (0)

If END2 == 1 or if END3 == 1

END4 How can we contact you? Please share your preferred way of contact with us.

Email address: _____

Facebook contact: _____

Phone number: _____

ABOUT THE PROJECT

What is the goal of this project?

The SYREALITY project wants to learn about the outlook of people from Syria in Europe, specifically about their life plans, their experiences in Europe and challenges they have faced. SYREALITY collects survey data in Austria, Germany, the Netherlands and Greece and in-depth interviews in Vienna, Berlin, Amsterdam and Athens. As part of the in-depth interviews, participants are also invited to draw maps about their daily life and their displacement trajectories.

Which countries are included?

SYREALITY covers Austria, Germany, the Netherlands and Greece. These countries were chosen because they all have seen large numbers of Syrians arriving since 2011 with different conditions regarding living conditions and the asylum procedure. This makes them highly relevant cases to study the relations between people's assessment of their life and their aspirations to settle down in a country. The study has a focus on cities as more than half of the world's displaced people live in urban areas.

Who is funding this research?

The study is funded by the Austrian Science Fund.

Who has reviewed this research project?

This project has been reviewed by the Austrian Science Fund and by external reviewers. The project was also reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee of the University for Continuing Education Krems, Austria.

Who is leading this research?

The SYREALITY project is led by Dr. Lea Müller-Funk of the University for Continuing Education Krems and supported by several research assistants. For information on all team members see here: .

YOUR INVOLVEMENT

What will you do with my data/answers?

We will use the data to write academic publications, blogs and policy briefs. From the survey, we will only use aggregate data such as averages (for example "60% of the people who answered the survey, indicated that they had voted in the last election", or "refugees who are often in touch with their family back home, more often remit money to their family members"). We will use the in-depth interviews to understand individual situations in more depth and cite parts of the stories in our writings. We will make sure that these excerpts do not reveal the identity of the speaker by citing short snippets.

Can I stop my participation in the study if I don't want to participate anymore?

You can stop your participation until the end of the project (2026).

Will I be compensated for taking part?

You will not receive any payment or compensation for your time.

DATA PROTECTION AND CONFIDENTIALITY

Will my participation in the study be confidential?

Your participation will be kept confidential.

Who will have access to the data?

Your answers will be stored in a dataset on a secure server that meets requirement of data protection laws. Only the project lead and researchers working in the project under the supervision of the project lead will have access to the datasets. These datasets will not contain your name or contact details. The project ends in 2026. After the end of the project, the datasets will be deposited in a 'data archive' for scientific data but access will remain restricted.

What information will you collect about me in the survey?

In addition to the answers you give to the survey, the survey software automatically collects your IP address. This is a unique number belonging to your internet connection. We will use the IP address only to check for irregularities (for example the same address being connected to multiple surveys, bots, or addresses linked to countries not included in our project). After this check, the IP address will be deleted from the datafiles.

What information will you collect about me in the in-depth interviews?

The in-depth interviews will cover the story of your whole life.

Can I access my personal study data?

You can only access the data of the in-depth interviews and the maps since the survey data will be completely anonymized. Please contact Dr. Lea Müller-Funk (lea.mueller-funk@donau-uni.ac.at) and you will be able to access the transcript of your in-depth interview and a scan of your maps.

I've indicated I'm willing to be contacted about a second round of the survey or a follow-up in-depth interview and entered my email address for this purpose. How will you store and use my email address?

Email addresses are stored in a file together with an ID number. The file with email addresses is separate from the dataset with answers to the survey questions and is only accessible to the project leader. All datafiles will be held on a secure server that meet data protection requirements regulations. The email addresses will only be used to send out a second survey and invite you for a qualitative interview. We will use the ID number to connect answers from the first and second survey. The file with email addresses will not be shared with anyone.

I've indicated I'm willing to be contacted about a second round of the survey and entered my email address. I have changed my mind. Can you remove my address from the file?

Yes we can. Please contact Dr. Lea Müller-Funk (lea.mueller-funk@donau-uni.ac.at) and your email address will be removed.

Who can I contact with questions or concerns?

You can contact Dr. Lea Müller-Funk (lea.mueller-funk@donau-uni.ac.at) or the head of the Ethics Committee of the University for Continuing Education Krems (ethikkommission@donau-uni.ac.at).

استبيان سيراليوتي | SYREALITY

University for
Continuing
Education Krems

مرحباً.

أنت مدعو للمشاركة في دراسة استقصائية حول تطلعات وخطط الحياة لدى السوريين الذين يعيشون في النمسا وألمانيا وهولندا واليونان لفهم كيف يخططون لحياتهم وما هي التحديات التي يواجهونها.

هذا الاستبيان هو جزء من مشروع بحثي بقيادة الدكتورة ليا مولر-فانك من جامعة كريمس للتعليم المستمر في النمسا. المشروع غير مرتبط بأي جهة حكومية إلا أن مشاركتك فيه قد تساعد المنظمات غير الحكومية وصناع القرار في اتخاذ قرارات مبنية على الأدلة التي نجمعها عبر هذا الاستبيان.

تضمن جامعة كريمس للتعليم المستمر أن تظل معلوماتك سرية حيث سيتم تخزينها على خادم آمن. لمزيد من المعلومات، انقر [هنا](#).

يمكنك ملء الاستبيان أدناه (باللغة العربية). لن يستغرق الأمر أكثر من 20 دقيقة. يرجى ملاحظة ما يلي: يجب أن يكون تاريخ ميلادك بين 1957 و 1996 للمشاركة.

إنك توافق من خلال إكمال هذا الاستبيان على المشاركة في دراستنا. شكراً لك سلفاً على مساعدتك وتعاونك.

هذا الاستبيان لا يسجل أي معلومات هوية

تسجيل إجاباتك على الإستبيان لا يتطلب أي معلومات عن هويتك ، إلا إذا كان الإستبيان يحتوي على بند خاص بطلب المعلومات الشخصية.

إذا استخدمت رمزاً مميزاً للوصول إلى هذا الاستطلاع ، يُرجى الاطمئنان إلى أن هذا الرمز المميز لن يتم تخزينه مع ردودك. تتم إدارته في قاعدة بيانات منفصلة وسيتم تحديثه فقط للإشارة إلى ما إذا كنت قد أكملت (أو لم تستكمل) هذا الاستطلاع. لا توجد طريقة لمطابقة رموز التعريف برموز الاستطلاع.

للمتابعة، يرجى أولاً قبول سياسة الخصوصية للاستبيان.
عرض السياسة

إشعار الخصوصية لمشروع البحث SYREALITY

مراقب (المادة 7/4 GDPR (اللائحة العامة لحماية البيانات))

جامعة كريمس للدراسات المستمرة (جامعة الدانوب كريمس)

قسم الهجرة والعولمة

Dr.-Karl-Dorrek-Straße 30 ;3500 Krems an der Donau، النمسا

مسؤول الاتصال: د. ليا مولر فونك (lea.mueller-funk@donau-uni.ac.at)

مسؤول حماية البيانات: دكتور دانيال ستانونيك والدكتور كارستن كيناست (datenschutz@donau-uni.ac.at)

الغرض من معالجة البيانات

جمع المعلومات لأغراض البحث المذكور أعلاه.

نقدم الاستبيان التالي عبر الإنترنت عبر بوابة LimeSurvey GmbH، LimeSurvey GmbH، Papeenreya 63، 22453 Hamburg، (ألمانيا) التي أبرمنا معها اتفاقية معالجة. عند الوصول إلى موقع الاستبيان، يتلقى LimeSurvey معلومات السجل، أي ملفات تعريف الارتباط الضرورية للمعالجة الفنية للاستبيان (التخزين المؤقت وما إلى ذلك). أنت تزودنا من خلال الاستبيان ببيانات حول المعلومات الديموغرافية الخاصة بك، ومسار الزواج، وخطط الحياة، وتطلعات الهجرة والبقاء، والأسئلة المتعلقة بالعمل والفقر والثروة، بالإضافة إلى الرضا عن الحياة والأمل. حتى ربط هذه البيانات ببعضها البعض لا يسمح لنا باستخلاص أي استنتاجات حول هويتك.

الأساس القانوني

المادة 89 جنبًا إلى جنب مع المادة 6 (1)، الفقرة e من اللائحة العامة لحماية البيانات جنبًا إلى جنب مع المادة 3، الفقرات 1، 7 و 8 من قانون الجامعة النمساوية (UG) [= تطوير العلوم (البحث والتدريس)؛ دعم التعاون الوطني والدولي في مجال البحث العلمي ؛ استخدام وتنفيذ نتائج البحث في الممارسة].

المستلمون

المشاركون المستهدفون في الاستطلاع هم الأشخاص المولودون في سوريا والذين تركوها بعد 2011 ويعيشون حاليًا في النمسا أو ألمانيا أو هولندا أو اليونان ممن تتراوح أعمارهم حاليًا بين 27 و 65 عامًا. لا يتم مشاركة بياناتك الشخصية مع أي جهات خارجية.

فترة التخزين

يتم تخزين معلومات السجل طوال مدة الجلسة. يمكن أرشفة بيانات الاستطلاع عبر الإنترنت إلى أجل غير مسمى بسبب عدم إمكانية التعرف على الهويات الفردية للمشاركين.

حقوقك

لممارسة حقك في الوصول إلى المعلومات أو مسحها أو ما إلى ذلك وفقًا للمادة 15-20 من القانون العام لحماية البيانات (GDPR)، يرجى الاتصال بشخص الاتصال المشار إليه أعلاه أو مسؤول حماية البيانات التابع له. إلا أنه نظرًا لعدم إمكانية تحديد هويتك، قد يتم تقييد حقوقك دون تقديم مزيد من المعلومات وفقًا للمادة 11 من القانون العام لحماية البيانات (GDPR). يمكنك تقديم شكاوى النهائية إلى هيئة الإشراف النمساوية عبر www.dsb.gov.at.

E1

نود أولاً أن نطرح عليك بعض الأسئلة المتعلقة بوضعك الشخصي.

هل ولدت في سورية؟

نعم (1)

لا (0)

If E1 == 0, end survey

E2

هل تحمل الجنسية السورية حالياً؟

نعم (1)

لا (0)

لا أعرف (97)

If E1 == 0 & E2 == 1 or

If E1 == 1 & E2 == 0 or

If E1 == 1 & E2 == 1

E3

في أي عام ولدت؟

1957

1958

1959

1960

1961

1962

1963

1964

1965

1966

1967

1968

1969

1970

1971

1972

1973

1974

1975

1976

1977

1978

- 1979
- 1980
- 1981
- 1982
- 1983
- 1984
- 1985
- 1986
- 1987
- 1988
- 1989
- 1990
- 1991
- 1992
- 1993
- 1994
- 1995
- 1996
- أخرى (999)

If E3 == 1957-1996

E4

هل غادرت سورية لآخر مرة بعد 2011؟

- نعم (1)
- لا (0)

If E4 == 1

E5

أين تعيش حالياً؟

- النمسا (1)
- ألمانيا (2)
- هولندا (3)
- اليونان، أو (4)
- دولة أخرى (5)

If E5 == 1, 2, 3 or 4

E6

منذ أي عام تعيش في [النمسا / ألمانيا / هولندا / اليونان]؟

- 2011
- 2012
- 2013
- 2014

- 2015 ○
- 2016 ○
- 2017 ○
- 2018 ○
- 2019 ○
- 2020 ○
- 2021 ○
- 2022 ○
- 2023 ○

If E1 == 0 & E2 == 0 OR

If E1 == 0 & E2 == 97 OR

If E3 == 999 OR

If E4 == 0 OR

If E5 == 5

END

للأسف أنت غير مؤهل للمشاركة في هذا الاستبيان. نحن نجري مقابلات مع السوريين المقيمين في النمسا وألمانيا وهولندا واليونان الذين غادروا سورية بعد عام 2011 ممن تتراوح تاريخ ميلادك بين 1957 و 1996.

الخصائص الديمغرافية | (DEM1) Demographics 1

DEM1

من فضلك قل لي، هل أنت...

- رجل (1)
- امرأة (2)
- غير ذلك (3)

DEM2

ما هو أعلى مستوى تعليمي أكملته؟

- لم أدخل المدرسة (1)
- ابتدائي (الصف 1-6) (2)
- إعدادي (الصف 7-9) (3)
- ثانوية عامة (الصف 10-12) (4)
- ثانوية فنون أو صناعة أو تجارة (الصف 10-12) (5)
- ما بعد الثانوي (معهد متوسط) (6)
- بكالوريوس جامعي (7)
- ماجستير جامعي (8)
- دكتوراه جامعية (9)

DEM3

ما هي حالتك الاجتماعية؟

- أعزب (1)

- متزوج أو في علاقة طويلة الأمد (2)
- مطلق أو أرمل (3)
- لا أعرف (97)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

DEM4

هل لديك أولاد حالياً؟

- نعم (1)
- لا (0)

تطلعات الحياة في الماضي والحاضر | (ASP) Life aspirations in the past and present

نود أن نسألك الآن عن رغباتك وخططك لحياتك من الماضي حتى الآن.

ASP1

أولاً، نود أن نعرف ما هو برأيك أهم شيء حدث في حياتك في آخر 15 عامًا؟ فكر مثلاً بحدث غير مسار حياتك مثل وفاة الزوج أو الطلاق أو ولادة طفل أو تغيير مهني أو تغيير مكان الإقامة.

ASP2

الآن سنتحدث عن خططك المتعلقة بالتعليم.
هل سبق لك أن رغبت بشدة في متابعة تعليمك أو البدء بتعلم شيء جديد؟
يمكن أن تكون الرغبة متعلقة بمواصلة التعليم في المدرسة أو الجامعة أو حضور ورش العمل أو تدريب مهني.

- نعم (1)
- لا (0)

If ASP2 == 1

ASP3

متى كانت لديك هذه الأمنية المتعلقة بالتعليم؟
يمكنك اختيار عدة خيارات.

- قبل عام 2011 (1)
- بين عام 2011 وحتى وصولي إلى أوروبا (2)
- منذ وصولي إلى أوروبا حتى الآن (3)

ASP4

هل انقطع تعليمك المدرسي أو الجامعي في سورية بسبب الحرب؟

- لا، لم اضطر لإيقاف دراستي. (1)
- نعم، ولم أستطع مواصلة دراستي حتى الآن. (2)
- نعم، لكن تمكنت من مواصلة دراستي قبل مجيئي إلى أوروبا. (3)
- نعم، لكن تمكنت من مواصلة دراستي في أوروبا. (4)
- لم أكن أدرس في ذلك الوقت. (5)

ASP00

الآن سنتحدث عن الأمنيات المتعلقة بالأسرة والعلاقات العاطفية في ثلاث فترات - في عام 2010، بين عام 2011 ووصولك إلى أوروبا ومنذ وصولي إلى أوروبا حتى الآن.

ASP5a

في عام 2010 ، هل رغبت بشدة في...

يمكنك اختيار عدة خيارات.

- الزواج وتكوين أسرة (1)
- العيش في نفس المنزل مع والديك / شريك / أطفالك. (2)
- بدء علاقة عاطفية مختلفة عما تتقبله العائلة (3) .
- التخلص من علاقة عاطفية أو الحصول أحصل على الطلاق(4) .
- تحسين علاقتك بشريكك العاطفي. (5)
- غير ذلك، يرجى التحديد _____(6)
- لا، ليس لدي أي أمنيات تتعلق بالأسرة والعلاقات. (7)

ASP5b

بين عام 2011 وحتى وصولي إلى أوروبا، هل رغبت بشدة في...

يمكنك اختيار عدة خيارات.

- الزواج وتكوين أسرة (1)
- العيش في نفس المنزل مع والديك / شريك / أطفالك. (2)
- بدء علاقة عاطفية مختلفة عما تتقبله العائلة (3) .
- التخلص من علاقة عاطفية أو الحصول أحصل على الطلاق(4) .
- تحسين علاقتك بشريكك العاطفي. (5)
- غير ذلك، يرجى التحديد _____(6)
- لا، ليس لدي أي أمنيات تتعلق بالأسرة والعلاقات. (7)

ASP5c

منذ وصولي إلى أوروبا حتى الآن، هل رغبت بشدة في...

يمكنك اختيار عدة خيارات.

- الزواج وتكوين أسرة (1)
- العيش في نفس المنزل مع والديك / شريك / أطفالك. (2)
- بدء علاقة عاطفية مختلفة عما تتقبله العائلة (3) .
- التخلص من علاقة عاطفية أو الحصول أحصل على الطلاق(4) .
- تحسين علاقتك بشريكك العاطفي. (5)
- غير ذلك، يرجى التحديد _____(6)
- لا، ليس لدي أي أمنيات تتعلق بالأسرة والعلاقات. (7)

ASP6a

الآن سنتحدث عن أمنياتك المتعلقة بالعمل في عام 2010، بين عام 2011 ووصولك إلى أوروبا ومنذ وصولك إلى أوروبا حتى الآن.

في عام 2010، هل كنت ترغب بشدة في ممارسة مهنة محددة في حياتك؟

نعم (1)

لا (0)

If ASP6a == 1

ASP6b

في عام 2010، ما هي المهنة التي تمنيت العمل بها؟
الرجاء اختيار الفئة التي تشعر أنها تناسبك بشكل أفضل.

- مسؤول رفيع المستوى (مثلاً: مصرفي، مدير تنفيذي في شركة كبيرة، مسؤول حكومي كبير، مسؤول نقابي، ضابط جيش برتبة عالية مثل رائد. (2)
- صاحب مهنة تقنية أو احترافية (مثلاً: طبيب، مدرس، مهندس، فنان، محاسب، ممرض، صف ضابط في الجيش مثل ملازم. (1)
- عامل مبيعات (مثلاً: مدير مبيعات، صاحب متجر، مساعد متجر، وكيل تأمين، وكيل مشتريات) (4)
- عمل مكثبي (مثلاً: سكرتير، كاتب، مدير مكتب، موظف مدني، كاتب حسابات) (3)
- عامل خدمة (مثلاً: صاحب مطعم، ضابط شرطة، نادل، حلاق، حارس، جندي) (5)
- عامل ماهر (مثلاً: مشرف على العمال، ميكانيكي سيارات، طباع، خياط، صانع الأدوات والقوالب، كهربائي) (6)
- عامل شبه ماهر (مثلاً: عامل بناء، سائق حافلة، عامل مدبغة، نجار، عامل صفائح معدنية، خباز) (7)
- عامل غير ماهر (مثلاً: عامل، حمال، عامل مصنع غير ماهر، عامل نظافة) (8)
- عامل مزرعة (مثلاً: عامل مزرعة، سائق جرار) (9)
- مالك مزرعة، مدير مزرعة (10)

ASP6c

بين عام 2011 وحتى وصولك إلى أوروبا، هل كنت ترغب بشدة في ممارسة مهنة محددة في حياتك؟

- نعم (1)
- لا (0)

If ASP6c== 1

ASP6d

بين عام 2011 وحتى وصولك إلى أوروبا، ما هي المهنة التي تمنيت العمل بها؟
الرجاء اختيار الفئة التي تشعر أنها تناسبك بشكل أفضل.

- مسؤول رفيع المستوى (مثلاً: مصرفي، مدير تنفيذي في شركة كبيرة، مسؤول حكومي كبير، مسؤول نقابي، ضابط جيش برتبة عالية مثل رائد. (2)
- صاحب مهنة تقنية أو احترافية (مثلاً: طبيب، مدرس، مهندس، فنان، محاسب، ممرض، صف ضابط في الجيش مثل ملازم. (1)
- عامل مبيعات (مثلاً: مدير مبيعات، صاحب متجر، مساعد متجر، وكيل تأمين، وكيل مشتريات) (4)
- عمل مكثبي (مثلاً: سكرتير، كاتب، مدير مكتب، موظف مدني، كاتب حسابات) (3)
- عامل خدمة (مثلاً: صاحب مطعم، ضابط شرطة، نادل، حلاق، حارس، جندي) (5)
- عامل ماهر (مثلاً: مشرف على العمال، ميكانيكي سيارات، طباع، خياط، صانع الأدوات والقوالب، كهربائي) (6)
- عامل شبه ماهر (مثلاً: عامل بناء، سائق حافلة، عامل مدبغة، نجار، عامل صفائح معدنية، خباز) (7)
- عامل غير ماهر (مثلاً: عامل، حمال، عامل مصنع غير ماهر، عامل نظافة) (8)
- عامل مزرعة (مثلاً: عامل مزرعة، سائق جرار) (9)
- مالك مزرعة، مدير مزرعة (10)

ASP6e

منذ وصولك إلى أوروبا حتى الآن، هل كنت ترغب بشدة في ممارسة مهنة محددة في حياتك؟

- نعم (1)
- لا (0)

If ASP6e == 1

ASP6f

منذ وصولك إلى أوروبا حتى الآن، ما هي المهنة التي تمنيت العمل بها؟

الرجاء اختيار الفئة التي تشعر أنها تناسبك بشكل أفضل.

- مسؤول رفيع المستوى (مثلاً: مصري، مدير تنفيذي في شركة كبيرة، مسؤول حكومي كبير، مسؤول نقابي، ضابط جيش برتبة عالية مثل رائد. (2)
- صاحب مهنة تقنية أو احترافية (مثلاً: طبيب، مدرس، مهندس، فنان، محاسب، ممرض، صف ضابط في الجيش مثل ملازم. (1)
- عامل مبيعات (مثلاً: مدير مبيعات، صاحب متجر، مساعد متجر، وكيل تأمين، وكيل مشتريات) (4)
- عمل مكتبي (مثلاً: سكرتير، كاتب، مدير مكتب، موظف مدني، كاتب حسابات) (3)
- عامل خدمة (مثلاً: صاحب مطعم، ضابط شرطة، نادل، حلاق، حارس، جندي) (5)
- عامل ماهر (مثلاً: مشرف على العمال، ميكانيكي سيارات، طباع، خياط، صانع الأدوات والقوالب، كهربائي) (6)
- عامل شبه ماهر (مثلاً: عامل بناء، سائق حافلة، عامل مدبغة، نجار، عامل صفائح معدنية، خباز) (7)
- عامل غير ماهر (مثلاً: عامل، حمال، عامل مصنع غير ماهر، عامل نظافة) (8)
- عامل مزرعة (مثلاً: عامل مزرعة، سائق جرار) (9)
- مالك مزرعة، مدير مزرعة (10)

ASP7

الآن سوف نتحدث عن أمنياتك المتعلقة بالتغيير الاجتماعي والسياسي.

هل سبق لك أن رغبت بشدة في تغيير التقاليد الاجتماعية و / أو الأوضاع السياسية في سورية؟

- نعم (1)
- لا (0)

If ASP7 == 1

ASP8

متى كان ذلك؟

يمكنك اختيار عدة خيارات.

- قبل عام 2011 (1)
- بين عام 2011 وحتى وصولي إلى أوروبا (2)
- منذ وصولي إلى أوروبا حتى الآن (3)

If ASP7 == 1

ASP9

هل قمت شخصياً بنشاط ما لتغيير التقاليد الاجتماعية و / أو الأوضاع السياسية في سورية، سواء في حياتك الخاصة أو في المجال العام؟

- نعم (1)
- لا (0)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

If ASP9 == 1

ASP10

هناك العديد من الأشياء التي يمكن للناس القيام بها لرؤية التغيير الاجتماعي والسياسي.

هل سبق وأن قمت بأي مما يلي؟

يمكنك اختيار عدة خيارات.

- شاركت في مجموعات محلية أو مبادرات شبابية (1)
- شاركت في إحدى منظمات المجتمع المدني (2)
- حاولت تغيير بعض العادات والتقاليد الاجتماعية في حياتي الخاصة. (3)
- عبرت عن رأيي السياسي علناً (في الإعلام، الاحتجاجات، حملات المناصرة، إلخ) (4)
- انضمت إلى حزب سياسي (5)
- شاركت في حركة سياسية غير حزبية (6)
- انضمت إلى جماعة مسلحة (7)
- قمت بإنشاء شبكات دعم بين الأفراد ذوي التفكير المماثل (8)
- غير ذلك، يرجى التحديد
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

ASP11

ما مدى اهتمامك بالسياسة هذه الأيام - هل أنت...

- مهتم جدًا (1)
- مهتم إلى حد ما (2)
- مهتم قليلاً (3)
- لست مهتم على الإطلاق (4)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

ASP12

هل تتابع الأحداث السياسية في سورية؟

- نعم إلى حد ما (1)
- لا مطلقاً (2)

ASP13

هل تتابع الأحداث السياسية في [النمسا / ألمانيا / هولندا / اليونان]؟

- نعم إلى حد ما (1)
- لا مطلقاً (2)

If ASP9 == 1:

FEMACT1

هل قمت شخصياً بأي نشاط من أجل المساواة بين الرجل والمرأة في سورية، سواء في الحياة الخاصة أو في المجال العام؟

- نعم (1)
- لا (0)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

If FEMACT1 == 1

FEMACT2

متى كان ذلك؟

يمكنك اختيار عدة خيارات.

- قبل عام 2011 (1)

- بين عام 2011 وحتى وصولي إلى أوروبا (2)
- منذ وصولي إلى أوروبا حتى الآن (3)

If FEMACT1 ==1

FEMACT3

ما الذي ألهمك للقيام بنشاط ما من أجل المساواة بين الرجل والمرأة؟
يمكنك اختيار عدة خيارات.

- ملاحظتي أن الرجال والنساء يعاملون بشكل غير عادل في مجتمعي (في سوريا أو في الخارج). (1)
- معاناتي الشخصية من التمييز و / أو العنف في سورية لأنني امرأة. (2)
- معاناتي الشخصية من التمييز و / أو العنف في الخارج لأنني امرأة. (3)
- حضوري تدريب/ات حول حقوق المرأة في سورية. (4)
- حضوري تدريب/ات حول حقوق المرأة في الخارج. (5)
- مطالعتي كتبًا عن النسوية وقضايا المرأة. (6)
- عملي في منظمة نسوية داخل سورية. (7)
- عملي في منظمة نسوية خارج سورية. (8)
- وجود شخص نسوي ملهم في حياتي مثل صديق/ة أو أحد أفراد الأسرة. (9)
- أسباب أخرى، يرجى التحديد: _____ (10)

If FEMACT1 ==1

FEMACT4

هل تُعرف عن نفسك بأنك نسوي؟

- نعم (1)
- لا (0)

مسار النزوح | Displacement trajectory (D)

شكرا لك على إجاباتك حتى الآن. الآن سوف نسألك حول الأماكن التي عشت فيها قبل عام 2011 وبعدها.

D1

في نهاية عام 2010، في أي محافظة كنت تعيش؟

- حلب (1)
- دمشق (2)
- درعا (3)
- دير الزور (4)
- حماه (5)
- الحسكة (6)
- حمص (7)
- إدلب (8)
- اللاذقية (9)
- القنيطرة (10)
- الرقة (11)
- ريف دمشق (12)

- السويداء (13)
- طرطوس (14)

D2

في نهاية عام 2010، هل كنت تعيش في منطقة...

- ريف (1)، أو
- مدينة؟ (2)

D3

هل نزحت داخل سورية بعد عام 2011؟

- نعم (1)
- لا (0)

D4

بعد 2011، في أي من مناطق السيطرة السياسية التالية عشت أطول فترة في سورية؟

- مناطق النظام (1)
- مناطق المعارضة (2)
- مناطق داعش (3)
- مناطق الإدارة الذاتية في شمال وشرق سوريا (4)
- أخرى، يرجى التحديد: _____ (5)
- لم أعش في سورية بعد آذار 2011 (6)
- لا أعرف (97)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

If D3 == 1

D5

بعد عام 2011، هل اضطرت للنزوح إلى مناطق سيطرة سياسية مختلفة في سورية؟

- نعم (1)
- لا (0)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

D6

لم أستطع البقاء في سوريا لأنني... (يمكنك اختيار عدة خيارات.)

- تعرضت أو كنت خائف من تهديد يستهدفني شخصيًا. (1)
- كنت أخشى من القصف. (2)
- كنت محروم من حرية التعبير. (3)
- لم أرغب في القتال إلى جانب أي طرف. (4)
- عانيت من سوء الوضع الاقتصادي. (5)
- لم يعد لدي مكان للإقامة بعد تدمير منزلي. (6)
- أردت الانضمام إلى أحد أفراد أسرتي في الخارج. (7)
- لم أتمكن من الوصول إلى التعليم. (8)
- لم أتمكن من الوصول إلى الخدمات الصحية. (9)

- سبب آخر، يرجى التحديد: _____ (10)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

D7a

- بعد عام 2011، هل عشت في دولة أخرى لمدة عام أو أكثر (باستثناء سورية و(النمسا ألمانيا هولندا اليونان))؟
- نعم (1)
 - لا (0)

If D7a == 1

D7b

في أي من الدول التالية عشت لمدة عام أو أكثر بعد عام 2011؟
يمكنك اختيار عدة خيارات.

- تركيا (1)
- الأردن (2)
- لبنان (3)
- مصر (4)
- المملكة العربية السعودية (5)
- الإمارات العربية المتحدة (6)
- اليونان (7)
- إيطاليا (8)
- المجر (9)
- النمسا (10)
- ألمانيا (11)
- هولندا (12)
- السويد (13)
- غير ذلك، يرجى التحديد _____ (14)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

D8

هل تعيش حالياً في منطقة...

- ريف (1)،
- مدينة (وليس العاصمة) (2)، أو
- العاصمة؟ (3)

D9

ما هو وضعك القانوني حالياً في هذا البلد؟

- لدي إقامة لاجئ أو حماية مؤقتة. (1)
- أنا طالب لجوء. (لازمت أنتظر الإجراءات) (2)
- تم رفض طلب اللجوء في هذا البلد. (3)
- إقامة طالب (4)
- إقامة عمل (5)
- لدي جنسية في هذا البلد. (6)

- لم أتقدم بطلب للحصول على أي إقامة في هذا البلد. (7)
- غير ذلك، يرجى التحديد _____ (8)
- لا أعرف (97)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

If D9 = 1, 4, 5

D10

في أي سنة حصلت على حق اللجوء / الإقامة؟

- 2011
- 2012
- 2013
- 2014
- 2015
- 2016
- 2017
- 2018
- 2019
- 2020
- 2021
- 2022
- 2023
- لا أعرف (97)

D11

كم مرة تتواصل مع العائلة و / أو الأصدقاء في سورية؟ (اتصال، دردشة، بريد إلكتروني، زيارة)

- حوالي مرة واحدة في الأسبوع (1)
- حوالي مرة واحدة في الشهر (2)
- حوالي مرة كل بضعة أشهر (3)
- حوالي مرة واحدة في السنة (4)
- أقل من مرة في السنة (5)
- لا أتواصل أبداً (6)
- ليس لدي عائلة ولا أصدقاء في سورية (7)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

D12

كم مرة تستخدم وسائل التواصل الاجتماعي مثل الفيسبوك، الواتساب، التلغرام أو السيجنال؟

يمكن أن يكون هذا للتواصل و / أو للترفيه.

- يومياً (1)
- عدة مرات في الأسبوع (2)
- مرة واحدة في الأسبوع (3)
- أقل من مرة في الأسبوع (4)
- أبداً (5)

D13

منذ وصولك إلى أوروبا، هل أنت (أو شريكك) مسؤول ماليًا عن أي فرد من أفراد الأسرة خارج الاتحاد الأوروبي؟

- نعم (1)
- لا (0)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

Asylum Policies (POL) | سياسات اللجوء

POL1

نحن الآن مهتمون برأيك حول الحياة هنا في أوروبا. هل تعتقد أن حياة السوريين في أوروبا بشكل عام...

- سيئة جدا (1)
- سيئة (2)
- ليس جيدة ولا سيئة (3)
- جيدة (4)
- جيدة جدًا (5)
- لا أعرف (97)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

POL2

هل تعتقد أن المساعدة المقدمة من الحكومة في [ألمانيا / النمسا / هولندا / اليونان] للسوريين المحتاجين المقيمين هنا، هي...

- سيئة جدا (1)
- سيئة (2)
- ليس جيدة ولا سيئة (3)
- جيدة (4)
- جيدة جدًا (5)
- لا أعرف (97)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

Migration and stay aspirations, now and in the future (MIG) | تطلعات الهجرة والبقاء الحالية والمستقبلية

الآن، نود أن نسألك بعض الأسئلة حول رأيك في إقامتك الحالية خارج سورية ورأيك بالانتقال للعيش في بلد آخر.

If D7a == 1

MIG1

في الفترة ما بين مغادرتك سوريا حتى وصولك إلى هنا، هل كنت ترغب في البقاء في البلد الذي نزلت إليه ولكنك لم تتمكن ذلك؟

- نعم (1)
- لا (0)
- لا أعرف (97)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

If D7a == 1 & MIG1 == 1

MIG2

في أي من الدول التالية؟
يمكنك اختيار عدة خيارات.

- تركيا (1)
- الأردن (2)
- لبنان (3)
- مصر (4)
- المملكة العربية السعودية (5)
- الإمارات العربية المتحدة (6)
- اليونان (7)
- إيطاليا (8)
- المجر (9)
- النمسا (10)
- ألمانيا (11)
- هولندا (12)
- السويد (13)
- غير ذلك، يرجى التحديد (14) _____

MIG3

قبل مجيئك للعيش في [النمسا / ألمانيا / هولندا / اليونان]، هل كان أي من أفراد عائلتك المقربة (يعني شريك أو والديك أو أولادك) يعيشون قبلك هنا؟

- نعم (1)
- لا (0)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

MIG4

هل ترغب في الذهاب إلى بلد آخر والعيش فيه في وقت ما خلال السنوات الخمس المقبلة، أم تفضل البقاء في [النمسا / ألمانيا / هولندا / اليونان]؟

- أفضل الذهاب إلى بلد آخر (1)
- أفضل البقاء هنا (2)
- لا أعرف (97)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

If MIG4 == 1

MIG5

إلى أي بلد ترغب الذهاب والعيش فيه في وقت ما خلال السنوات الخمس المقبلة؟

- أثيوبيا 1
- أذربيجان 2
- الأردن 3
- أرمينيا 4
- إسبانيا 5
- أستراليا 6

- إستونيا 7
- أفغانستان 8
- ألبانيا 9
- ألمانيا 10
- الإمارات العربية المتحدة 11
- إندونيسيا 12
- أوكرانيا 13
- إيران 14
- أيرلندا 15
- أيسلندا 16
- إيطاليا 17
- باكستان 18
- البحرين 19
- البرتغال 20
- بروناي 21
- بلجيكا 22
- بلغاريا 23
- البوسنة والهرسك 24
- بولندا 25
- بيلاروسيا 26
- تركمانستان 27
- تونس 28
- الجبل الأسود 29
- الجزائر 30
- الجمهورية التشيكية 31
- جنوب أفريقيا 32
- جنوب السودان 33
- جورجيا 34
- جيبوتي 35
- الدنمارك 36
- دولة قطر 37
- ديك رومي 38
- روسيا 39
- رومانيا 40
- سلطنة عمان 41
- سلوفاكيا 42
- سلوفينيا 43
- سنغافورة 44
- السويد 45
- سويسرا 46
- صربيا 47
- العراق 48

- فرنسا 49
- فلسطين 50
- فنلندا 51
- فيليبيني 52
- قبرص 53
- كرواتيا 54
- كندا 55
- كوسوفو 56
- الكويت 57
- لاتفيا 58
- لبنان 59
- لوكسمبورغ 60
- ليبيا 61
- ليتوانيا 62
- ليختنشتاين 63
- مالطا 64
- ماليزيا 65
- مصر 66
- المغرب 67
- مقدونيا 68
- المملكة العربية السعودية 69
- المملكة المتحدة 70
- موريتانيا 71
- مولدوفا 72
- موناكو 73
- النرويج 74
- النمسا 75
- نيوزيلاندا 76
- الهند 77
- هنغاريا 78
- هولندا 79
- الولايات المتحدة الأمريكية 80
- اليمن 81
- اليونان 82
- أخرى، يرجى التحديد: _____
- لا أعرف (97)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

MIG6

منذ وصولك إلى هذا البلد، هل سبق لك وأن خططت للانتقال والعيش في بلد آخر و لم تتمكن من ذلك؟

- نعم (1)
- لا (0)

○ أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

MIG7

هل ترغب في تغيير مكان إقامتك الحالي في (النمسا / ألمانيا / هولندا / اليونان)؟

- نعم (1)
○ لا (0)
○ لا أعرف (97)
○ أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

MIG8

هل ترغب في العودة للعيش في سورية في السنوات الخمس المقبلة؟

- نعم (1)
○ لا (0)
○ أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

MIG9

هناك بعض السوريين فكروا بالعودة إلى سورية لأسباب مختلفة. هل فكرت أنت يومًا في العودة ولكنك لم تتمكن من ذلك؟

- نعم (1)
○ لا (0)
○ لا أعرف (97)
○ أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

MIG10

هل ترغب في العودة للعيش في سورية في وقت ما في المستقبل في حال أصبحت آمنة؟

- نعم (1)
○ لا (0)
○ لا أعرف (97)
○ أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

If MIG10 == 1

MIG11

مالذي تتمنى أن يحدث في سوريا لكي تقول إن العودة إليها أصبحت آمنة؟

No mandatory question, option "no answer"

Demographics 2 (DEM) | الخصائص الديمغرافية 2

If DEM3 == 2

DEM5

نود الآن أن نطرح عليك بعض الأسئلة الأخرى حول وضعك الشخصي.

أين يعيش زوجك أو شريكك حاليًا؟

- معي في نفس المنزل (1)

- ليس معي في المنزل لكننا نقيم في نفس البلد (2)
- في بلد آخر (3)
- لا أعرف (97)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

If DEM4 == 1

DEM6

هل يعيش أولادك معك حالياً في [النمسا / ألمانيا / هولندا / اليونان]؟

- نعم، كلهم (1)
- نعم، بعضهم (2)
- لا، لا أحد منهم (3)
- لا أعرف (97)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

DEM7

ما هي ديانتك؟

- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)
- مسلم سني (1)
- مسلم شيعي (2)
- مسلم علوي (3)
- مسلم آخر (4)
- درزي (5)
- يزيدي (6)
- مسيحي (7)
- يهودي (8)
- لا دين أو ملحد (9)
- ديانة أخرى، يرجى التحديد (10)
- لا أعرف (97)

DEM8

ما هي اللغة التي كنت تتحدث بها في المنزل مع والديك عندما كنت طفلاً؟

يمكنك اختيار عدة خيارات.

- العربية (1)
- الكردية (2)
- التركية (3)
- الأرمنية (4)
- أخرى، يرجى التحديد: _____ (5)

DEM9

بأي لغة/ات أخرى يمكنك إجراء محادثة حول أمور الحياة اليومية؟

يمكنك اختيار عدة خيارات.

- العربية (1)

- الكردية (2)
- التركية (3)
- الأرمينية (4)
- الإنجليزية (5)
- الفرنسية (6)
- ألماني (7)
- الهولندية (8)
- اليونانية (9)
- أخرى، يرجى التحديد: _____ (10)
- أنا لا أتحدث لغة أخرى (11)

العمل والفقير والثروة | Work, poverty, and wealth (WPW)

WPW1

نود الآن معرفة المزيد عن خبراتك في العمل وعن وضعك الاقتصادي.
هل سبق لك أن قمت بأي عمل مدفوع الأجر بما في ذلك عملك الخاص؟

- نعم (1)
- لا (0)

If WPW1 == 1

WPW2

ما هو أفضل وصف مما يلي لأطول وظيفة مدفوعة الأجر عملت بها؟
الرجاء اختيار الفئة التي تشعر أنها تناسبك بشكل أفضل.

- مسؤول رفيع المستوى (مثلاً: مصري، مدير تنفيذي في شركة كبيرة، مسؤول حكومي كبير، مسؤول نقابي، ضابط جيش برتبة عالية مثل رائد. (2)
- صاحب مهنة تقنية أو احترافية (مثلاً: طبيب، مدرس، مهندس، فنان، محاسب، ممرض، صف ضابط في الجيش مثل ملازم. (1)
- عامل مبيعات (مثلاً: مدير مبيعات، صاحب متجر، مساعد متجر، وكيل تأمين، وكيل مشتريات) (4)
- عمل مكتبي (مثلاً: سكرتير، كاتب، مدير مكتب، موظف مدني، كاتب حسابات) (3)
- عامل خدمة (مثلاً: صاحب مطعم، ضابط شرطة، نادل، حلاق، حارس، جندي) (5)
- عامل ماهر (مثلاً: مشرف على العمال، ميكانيكي سيارات، طباع، خياط، صانع الأدوات والقوالب، كهربائي) (6)
- عامل شبه ماهر (مثلاً: عامل بناء، سائق حافلة، عامل مدبغة، نجار، عامل صفائح معدنية، خباز) (7)
- عامل غير ماهر (مثلاً: عامل، حمال، عامل مصنع غير ماهر، عامل نظافة) (8)
- عامل مزرعة (مثلاً: عامل مزرعة، سائق جرار) (9)
- مالك مزرعة، مدير مزرعة (10)

If WPW1 == 1

WPW3

هل كانت هذه المهنة هي أيضًا مهنتك الرئيسية قبل عام 2011؟

- نعم (1)
- لا (0)

If WPW3 == 0

WPW4

ما هو أفضل وصف مما يلي لأطول وظيفة مدفوعة الأجر عملت بها قبل عام 2011؟
الرجاء اختيار الفئة التي تشعر أنها تناسبك بشكل أفضل.

- مسؤول رفيع المستوى (مثلاً: مصري، مدير تنفيذي في شركة كبيرة، مسؤول حكومي كبير، مسؤول نقابي، ضابط جيش برتبة عالية مثل رائد. (2)
- صاحب مهنة تقنية أو احترافية (مثلاً: طبيب، مدرس، مهندس، فنان، محاسب، ممرض، صف ضابط في الجيش مثل ملازم. (1)
- عامل مبيعات (مثلاً: مدير مبيعات، صاحب متجر، مساعد متجر، وكيل تأمين، وكيل مشتريات) (4)
- عمل مكتبي (مثلاً: سكرتير، كاتب، مدير مكتب، موظف مدني، كاتب حسابات) (3)
- عامل خدمة (مثلاً: صاحب مطعم، ضابط شرطة، نادل، حلاق، حارس، جندي) (5)
- عامل ماهر (مثلاً: مشرف على العمال، ميكانيكي سيارات، طباع، خياط، صانع الأدوات والقوالب، كهربائي) (6)
- عامل شبه ماهر (مثلاً: عامل بناء، سائق حافلة، عامل مدبغة، نجار، عامل صفائح معدنية، خباز) (7)
- عامل غير ماهر (مثلاً: عامل، حمال، عامل مصنع غير ماهر، عامل نظافة) (8)
- عامل مزرعة (مثلاً: عامل مزرعة، سائق جرار) (9)
- مالك مزرعة، مدير مزرعة (10)
- لم يكن لدي عمل قبل عام 2011 (11)

If WPW1 == 1 & D7 == 1

WPW5

الآن أود أن تفكر في الفترة ما بين يوم مغادرتك سورية حتى وصولك إلى [النمسا / ألمانيا / هولندا / اليونان].
ما هو أفضل وصف مما يلي لأطول وظيفة مدفوعة الأجر عملت بها منذ مغادرتك سورية حتى وصولك إلى هنا؟
الرجاء اختيار الفئة التي تشعر أنها تناسبك بشكل أفضل.

- لم يكن لدي عمل في تلك الفترة (11)
- مسؤول رفيع المستوى (مثلاً: مصري، مدير تنفيذي في شركة كبيرة، مسؤول حكومي كبير، مسؤول نقابي، ضابط جيش برتبة عالية مثل رائد. (2)
- صاحب مهنة تقنية أو احترافية (مثلاً: طبيب، مدرس، مهندس، فنان، محاسب، ممرض، صف ضابط في الجيش مثل ملازم. (1)
- عامل مبيعات (مثلاً: مدير مبيعات، صاحب متجر، مساعد متجر، وكيل تأمين، وكيل مشتريات) (4)
- عمل مكتبي (مثلاً: سكرتير، كاتب، مدير مكتب، موظف مدني، كاتب حسابات) (3)
- عامل خدمة (مثلاً: صاحب مطعم، ضابط شرطة، نادل، حلاق، حارس، جندي) (5)
- عامل ماهر (مثلاً: مشرف على العمال، ميكانيكي سيارات، طباع، خياط، صانع الأدوات والقوالب، كهربائي) (6)
- عامل شبه ماهر (مثلاً: عامل بناء، سائق حافلة، عامل مدبغة، نجار، عامل صفائح معدنية، خباز) (7)
- عامل غير ماهر (مثلاً: عامل، حمال، عامل مصنع غير ماهر، عامل نظافة) (8)
- عامل مزرعة (مثلاً: عامل مزرعة، سائق جرار) (9)
- مالك مزرعة، مدير مزرعة (10)

If WPW1 == 1

WPW6

- الآن سنتحدث عن عملك الحالي. ما هو أفضل وصف لوضعك الحالي في العمل في [النمسا / ألمانيا / هولندا / اليونان]؟
- لدي وظيفة بدوام كامل (1)
 - أعمل بدوام جزئي (2)
 - لدي عمل صغير أو غير منتظم (3)
 - أقوم بتدريب مهني أو بعمل تطوعي (4)
 - أنا عاطل عن العمل مؤقتاً (5)
 - أنا مسؤول عن رعاية أفراد الأسرة والتسوق والأعمال المنزلية (6)

- أنا متقاعد (7)
- أنا طالب (مدرسة، ثانوية، جامعة، دراسة اللغة) (8)

If WPW6 == 1, 2, or 3

WPW7

ما هو أفضل وصف لعملك الحالي مما يلي في [النمسا / ألمانيا / هولندا / اليونان]؟
الرجاء اختيار الفئة التي تشعر أنها تناسبك بشكل أفضل.

- مسؤول رفيع المستوى (مثلاً: مصري، مدير تنفيذي في شركة كبيرة، مسؤول حكومي كبير، مسؤول نقابي، ضابط جيش برتبة عالية مثل رائد. (2)
- صاحب مهنة تقنية أو احترافية (مثلاً: طبيب، مدرس، مهندس، فنان، محاسب، ممرض، صف ضابط في الجيش مثل ملازم. (1)
- عامل مبيعات (مثلاً: مدير مبيعات، صاحب متجر، مساعد متجر، وكيل تأمين، وكيل مشتريات) (4)
- عمل مكتبي (مثلاً: سكرتير، كاتب، مدير مكتب، موظف مدني، كاتب حسابات) (3)
- عامل خدمة (مثلاً: صاحب مطعم، ضابط شرطة، نادل، حلاق، حارس، جندي) (5)
- عامل ماهر (مثلاً: مشرف على العمال، ميكانيكي سيارات، طباع، خياط، صانع الأدوات والقوالب، كهربائي) (6)
- عامل شبه ماهر (مثلاً: عامل بناء، سائق حافلة، عامل مدبغة، نجار، عامل صفائح معدنية، خباز) (7)
- عامل غير ماهر (مثلاً: عامل، حمال، عامل مصنع غير ماهر، عامل نظافة) (8)
- عامل مزرعة (مثلاً: عامل مزرعة، سائق جرار) (9)
- مالك مزرعة، مدير مزرعة (10)

If WPW1 == 0 & DEM3 == 2

WPW8

هل سبق وأن قام زوجك أو شريكك بأي عمل مدفوع الأجر بما في ذلك عمله لحسابه الخاص؟

- نعم (1)
- لا (0)

If WPW1 == 0 & DEM3 == 2 & WPW8 == 1

WPW9

ما هو أفضل وصف لأطول وظيفة مدفوعة الأجر عمل بها زوجك أو شريكك؟
الرجاء اختيار الفئة التي تشعر أنها تناسب بشكل أفضل.

- مسؤول رفيع المستوى (مثلاً: مصري، مدير تنفيذي في شركة كبيرة، مسؤول حكومي كبير، مسؤول نقابي، ضابط جيش برتبة عالية مثل رائد. (2)
- صاحب مهنة تقنية أو احترافية (مثلاً: طبيب، مدرس، مهندس، فنان، محاسب، ممرض، صف ضابط في الجيش مثل ملازم. (1)
- عامل مبيعات (مثلاً: مدير مبيعات، صاحب متجر، مساعد متجر، وكيل تأمين، وكيل مشتريات) (4)
- عمل مكتبي (مثلاً: سكرتير، كاتب، مدير مكتب، موظف مدني، كاتب حسابات) (3)
- عامل خدمة (مثلاً: صاحب مطعم، ضابط شرطة، نادل، حلاق، حارس، جندي) (5)
- عامل ماهر (مثلاً: مشرف على العمال، ميكانيكي سيارات، طباع، خياط، صانع الأدوات والقوالب، كهربائي) (6)
- عامل شبه ماهر (مثلاً: عامل بناء، سائق حافلة، عامل مدبغة، نجار، عامل صفائح معدنية، خباز) (7)
- عامل غير ماهر (مثلاً: عامل، حمال، عامل مصنع غير ماهر، عامل نظافة) (8)
- عامل مزرعة (مثلاً: عامل مزرعة، سائق جرار) (9)
- مالك مزرعة، مدير مزرعة (10)

If WPW1 == 0 & DEM3 == 1, 3, or 97 OR

If WPW1 == 0 & DEM3 == 2 & WPW8 == 0

WPW10

عندما كان عمرك 14 عامًا، كان والدك...

- يعمل كموظف، (1)
- لديه عمل حر أو تجاري أو مزرعة، (2)
- لا يعمل، (3)
- متوفي / مفقود (4)
- لا أعرف (97)

If WPW10 == 1, 2

WPW11

عندما كان عمرك 14 عامًا، ماذا ممايلي كان يمثل أفضل وصف لوظيفة والدك؟

الرجاء اختيار الفئة التي تشعر أنها تناسب بشكل أفضل.

- مسؤول رفيع المستوى (مثلاً: مصرفي، مدير تنفيذي في شركة كبيرة، مسؤول حكومي كبير، مسؤول نقابي، ضابط جيش برتبة عالية مثل رائد. (2)
- صاحب مهنة تقنية أو احترافية (مثلاً: طبيب، مدرس، مهندس، فنان، محاسب، ممرض، صف ضابط في الجيش مثل ملازم. (1)
- عامل مبيعات (مثلاً: مدير مبيعات، صاحب متجر، مساعد متجر، وكيل تأمين، وكيل مشتريات) (4)
- عمل مكتبي (مثلاً: سكرتير، كاتب، مدير مكتب، موظف مدني، كاتب حسابات) (3)
- عامل خدمة (مثلاً: صاحب مطعم، ضابط شرطة، نادل، حلاق، حارس، جندي) (5)
- عامل ماهر (مثلاً: مشرف على العمال، ميكانيكي سيارات، طباع، خياط، صانع الأدوات والقوالب، كهربائي) (6)
- عامل شبه ماهر (مثلاً: عامل بناء، سائق حافلة، عامل مدبغة، نجار، عامل صفائح معدنية، خباز) (7)
- عامل غير ماهر (مثلاً: عامل، حمال، عامل مصنع غير ماهر، عامل نظافة) (8)
- عامل مزرعة (مثلاً: عامل مزرعة، سائق جرار) (9)
- مالك مزرعة، مدير مزرعة (10)
- لا أعرف (97)

WPW12

في عام 2010، أي من العبارات التالية كانت تصف تقريباً وضعك المالي آنذاك؟

- لم يكن لدينا في الغالب ما يكفي من المال حتى لشراء الطعام (1)
- كان لدينا ما يكفي من المال ولكن فقط للأشياء الضرورية (2)
- كان لدينا ما يكفي من المال، ولكن كان علينا الاقتراض / الادخار لشراء أشياء باهظة الثمن، مثل البراد والتلفزيون (3)
- كان بإمكاننا تحمل تكاليف مشتريات باهظة الثمن دون صعوبة كبيرة، لكن شراء سيارة كان أمراً صعباً (4)
- كان بإمكاننا شراء سيارة دون بذل مجهود كبير، لكن شراء منزل كان مستحيلاً (5)
- كان بإمكاننا الحصول أي شيء نريده (6)
- لا أعرف (97)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

WPW13

في عام 2010، هل كنت تمتلك أنت أو عائلتك أي ممتلكات (منزل، عمل، أو أرض)؟

يمكنك اختيار عدة خيارات.

- نعم، منزل أو أكثر (1)
- نعم، عمل تجاري أو أكثر (2)
- نعم، أرض (3)

- لا، لم نمتلك شيئاً مما سبق (4)
 - لا أعرف (97)
- No mandatory question, option "no answer"*

WPW14

- بعد 2011، هل تم نهب ممتلكاتك الشخصية أو مصادرتها أو تدميرها؟
- نعم، جميعها (1)
 - نعم، بعضها (2)
 - لا (0)
 - لا أعرف (97)
 - أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

If WPW13 == 1,2, or 3

WPW15

- بعد 2011، هل فقدت أي من الوثائق الخاصة بممتلكاتك؟
- نعم، جميعها (1)
 - نعم، بعضها (2)
 - لا (0)
 - لا أعرف (97)
 - أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

WPW16

- أي من العبارات التالية هي الأفضل لوصف وضعك المادي في الفترة التي غادرت فيها سوريا؟
- لم يكن لدينا في الغالب ما يكفي من المال حتى لشراء الطعام (1)
 - كان لدينا ما يكفي من المال ولكن فقط للأشياء الضرورية (2)
 - كان لدينا ما يكفي من المال، ولكن كان علينا الاقتراض / الادخار لشراء أشياء باهظة الثمن، مثل البراد والتلفزيون (3)
 - كان بإمكاننا تحمل تكاليف مشتريات باهظة الثمن دون صعوبة كبيرة، لكن شراء سيارة كان أمراً صعباً (4)
 - كان بإمكاننا شراء سيارة دون بذل مجهود كبير، لكن شراء منزل كان مستحيلاً (5)
 - كان بإمكاننا الحصول أي شيء نريده (6)
 - لا أعرف (97)
 - أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

WPW17

- كيف تغير وضعك المادي منذ وصولك إلى [هذه الدولة] حتى الآن؟
- تحسن بشكل ملحوظ (1)
 - تحسن نوعاً ما (2)
 - لم يتغير (3)
 - تدهور إلى حد ما (4)
 - أصبح أسوأ بكثير (5)
 - لا أعرف (97)
 - أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

WPW18

انظر إلى الصورة. تخيل أن هذا السلم يمثل مكانة الناس في المجتمع السوري قبل عام 2011. في أعلى السلم، يوجد الأشخاص الذين لديهم أكبر قدر من المال و الشهادات العلمية وأفضل الوظائف. وفي الجزء السفلي يوجد الأشخاص الأكثر فقراً والأقل تعليماً ومن يعملون بأسوأ الوظائف أو من ليس لديهم وظيفة على الإطلاق. من فضلك قم باختيار الدرجة التي تعتقد أنها كانت تمثل مكانتك الاجتماعية في سورية قبل 2011.

- 10 أعلى السلم
- 9
- 8
- 7
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 أسفل السلم
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

WPW19

انظر إلى الصورة مرة أخرى وفكر في اللحظة التي غادرت فيها سورية، ثم قم من فضلك باختيار درجة السلم التي تعتقد أنها كانت تمثل مكانتك الاجتماعية في سورية عندما غادرتها.

- 10 أعلى السلم
- 9
- 8
- 7
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 أسفل السلم
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

WPW20

انظر إلى الصورة مرة أخرى وفكر في المجتمع هنا في (النمسا / ألمانيا / هولندا / اليونان) وموقفك اليوم. ثم قم من فضلك باختيار درجة السلم التي تعتقد أنها تمثل مكانتك الاجتماعية في (النمسا / ألمانيا / هولندا / اليونان).

- 10 أعلى السلم

- 9 ○
- 8 ○
- 7 ○
- 6 ○
- 5 ○
- 4 ○
- 3 ○
- 2 ○
- 1 أسفل السلم ○
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98) ○

الرضا عن الحياة والأمل | (SAT) Life satisfaction and hope

SAT1a

أنت على وشك الانتهاء لكن قبل أن تنتهي نود أن نعرف المزيد عن شعورك تجاه حياتك هذه الأيام.
كيف تسير أمور حياتك بشكل عام هذه الأيام؟
10 يشير إلى ممتاز و 1 يشير إلى سيء جدًا.

- 10 ممتاز ○
- 9 ○
- 8 ○
- 7 ○
- 6 ○
- 5 ○
- 4 ○
- 3 ○
- 2 ○
- 1 سيئ جدًا ○
- لا أعرف (97) ○
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98) ○

SAT1b

ما مدى رضاك بشكل عام عن حياتك هذه الأيام؟
10 يشير إلى أعلى درجة من الرضا و 1 يشير إلى أدنى درجة من الرضا.
10 أعلى درجة من الرضا ○

- 9 ○
- 8 ○
- 7 ○
- 6 ○
- 5 ○
- 4 ○
- 3 ○
- 2 ○

- 1 أدنى درجة من الرضا
- لا أعرف (97)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

SAT2

ما مدى رضاك حاليًا عن صحتك النفسية هذه الأيام؟

10 يشير إلى أعلى درجة من الرضا و 1 يشير إلى أدنى درجة من الرضا.

- 10 أعلى درجة من الرضا
- 9
- 8
- 7
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 أدنى درجة من الرضا
- لا أعرف (97)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

SAT3

ما مدى تفاؤلك هذه الأيام بشأن مستقبلك في أوروبا؟

10 يشير إلى أعلى قدر من الأمل و 1 يشير إلى أدنى قدر من الأمل.

- 10 أعلى قدر من الأمل
- 9
- 8
- 7
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 أدنى قدر من الأمل
- لا أعرف (97)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

SAT4

ما مدى تفاؤلك هذه الأيام بشأن مستقبل سورية؟

10 يشير إلى أعلى قدر من الأمل و 1 يشير إلى أدنى قدر من الأمل.

- 10 أعلى قدر من الأمل
- 9
- 8

- 7
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 أدنى قدر من الأمل
- لا أعرف (97)
- أفضل عدم الإجابة (98)

SAT5

ماذا تفعل عادة للتخفيف عن نفسك هذه الأيام؟

No mandatory question, option "no answer"

END1

لقد وصلنا إلى نهاية الاستبيان. نود أن نعرف ما هو انطباعك عن هذا الاستبيان بشكل عام؟

END2

نشكرك على الوقت الذي قضيتَه في الإجابة على أسئلتنا! نود أن نرسل لك استبياناً آخر مدته أقصر بعد بضع سنوات من الآن لنرى كيف أصبح حالك. هل لديك الرغبة في المشاركة بذلك؟

- نعم، ربما (1)
- لا، بالتأكيد لا أريد المشاركة مرة أخرى (0)

If D8 == 3

END3

هناك أيضاً فرصة لك لمشاركتنا المزيد عن تجاربك الحياتية في مقابلة شخصية. هل سيكون لديك الرغبة في المشاركة بها؟

- نعم، قد أكون على استعداد (1)
- لا، بالتأكيد لا أريد المشاركة في المقابلة (0)

If END2 == 1 or if END3 == 1

END4

من فضلك قم بتزويدنا بالطريقة المفضلة للتواصل معك؟

- بريدك الإلكتروني: _____
- حسابك على الفيسبوك: _____
- رقم الهاتف: _____

حول المشروع

ما هو الهدف من هذا المشروع؟

يريد مشروع SYREALITY التعرف على آفاق الناس من سوريا في أوروبا، وتحديدًا عن خطط حياتهم وتجاربهم في أوروبا والتحديات التي واجهوها. تجمع SYREALITY بيانات المسح في النمسا وألمانيا وهولندا واليونان والمقابلات المعمقة في فيينا وبرلين وأمستردام وأثينا. كجزء من المقابلات المتعمقة، يُدعى المشاركون أيضًا لرسم خرائط حول حياتهم اليومية ومسارات نزوحهم.

ما هي الدول المشمولة؟

تغطي SYREALITY النمسا وألمانيا وهولندا واليونان. تم اختيار هذه البلدان لأنها شهدت جميعًا وصول أعداد كبيرة من السوريين منذ عام 2011 بظروف مختلفة تتعلق بظروف المعيشة وإجراءات اللجوء مما يجعلهم حالات وثيقة الصلة بدراسة العلاقات بين تقييم الناس لحياتهم وتطلعاتهم إلى الاستقرار في بلد ما. تركز الدراسة على المدن التي يعيش فيها أكثر من نصف النازحين في العالم في مناطق حضرية.

من يمول هذا البحث؟

يتم تمويل الدراسة من قبل صندوق العلوم النمساوي.

من قام بمراجعة هذا المشروع البحثي؟

تمت مراجعة هذا المشروع من قبل صندوق العلوم النمساوي ومن قبل مراجعين خارجيين. تمت مراجعة المشروع أيضًا والموافقة عليه من قبل لجنة الأخلاقيات بجامعة التعليم المستمر في Krems، النمسا.

من يقود هذا البحث؟

يقود مشروع SYREALITY د. ليا مولر-فونك من جامعة Krems للتعليم المستمر وبدعم من العديد من الباحثين المساعدين. للحصول على معلومات حول جميع أعضاء الفريق انظر هنا:.

مشاركتك

كيف سوف تستخدم بياناتي / إجاباتي؟

سنستخدم البيانات لكتابة المنشورات الأكاديمية والمدونات وأوراق السياسات. سنستخدم فقط البيانات التي تم جمعها من خلال هذا الاستبيان مثل المتوسطات (على سبيل المثال "60% من الأشخاص الذين أجابوا على الاستبيان، أشاروا إلى أنهم صوتوا في الانتخابات الأخيرة"، أو "اللاجئون الذين غالبًا ما يكونون على اتصال بعائلاتهم. في المنزل، في كثير من الأحيان يقومون بتحويل الأموال إلى أفراد أسرهم"). سنستخدم المقابلات المتعمقة لفهم المواقف الفردية بمزيد من العمق والاستشهاد بأجزاء من القصص في كتاباتنا. سوف نتأكد من أن هذه المقطعات لا تكشف عن هوية المتحدث/ة من خلال الاستشهاد بمقتطفات قصيرة.

هل يمكنني إيقاف مشاركتي في الدراسة إذا لم أعد أرغب في المشاركة؟

يمكنك إيقاف مشاركتك حتى نهاية المشروع (2026).

هل سيتم تعويضني عن المشاركة؟

لن تتلقى أي مدفوعات أو تعويضات عن وقتك.

حماية البيانات والسرية

هل ستكون مشاركتي في الدراسة سرية؟

ستبقى مشاركتك سرية.

من سيكون له حق الوصول إلى البيانات؟

سيتم تخزين إجاباتك في قاعدة بيانات على خادم آمن متوافق مع متطلبات قوانين حماية البيانات. لن يتمكن من الوصول إلى قاعدة البيانات إلا قائدة المشروع والباحثون العاملون في المشروع تحت إشراف قائدة المشروع. لن تحتوي قاعدة البيانات هذه على اسمك أو تفاصيل الاتصال بك. ينتهي المشروع في عام 2026. بعد انتهاء المشروع، سيتم إيداع قاعدة البيانات في "أرشيف بيانات" للبيانات العلمية ولكن سيظل الوصول إليها مقيدًا.

ما هي المعلومات التي ستجمعها عني في الاستطلاع؟

بالإضافة إلى الإجابات التي تقدمها في الاستبيان، يقوم برنامج الاستبيان تلقائيًا بتسجيل عنوان IP الخاص بك. هذا رقم فريد يخص اتصالك بالإنترنت. سنستخدم عنوان IP فقط للتحقق من المخالفات (على سبيل المثال، يتم توصيل نفس العنوان بالعديد من الاستطلاعات أو الروبوتات أو العناوين المرتبطة ببلدان غير مدرجة في مشروعنا). بعد هذا الفحص، سيتم حذف عنوان IP من قاعدة البيانات.

ما هي المعلومات التي ستجمعها عني في المقابلات المعمقة؟

ستغطي المقابلات المعمقة قصة حياتك كلها.

هل يمكنني الوصول إلى بيانات الدراسة الشخصية الخاصة بي؟

يمكنك فقط الوصول إلى بيانات المقابلات المعمقة والخرائط لأن بيانات المسح ستكون مجهولة المصدر تمامًا. يرجى الاتصال بالدكتور ليا مولر فونك (lea.mueller-funk@donau-uni.ac.at) وستتمكن من الوصول إلى نص مقابلتك المعمقة ومسح خرائطك.

لقد أشرت إلى أنني على استعداد للاتصال بي بشأن الجولة الثانية من الاستطلاع أو لإجراء مقابلة متابعة معمقة، وأدخلت عنوان بريدي الإلكتروني لهذا الغرض. كيف سيتم تخزين واستخدام عنوان بريدي الإلكتروني؟

يتم تخزين عناوين البريد الإلكتروني في ملف مع رقم معرف. الملف الذي يحتوي على عناوين بريد إلكتروني منفصل عن قاعدة البيانات التي تحتوي على إجاباتك على أسئلة الاستبيان ولا يمكن الوصول إليها إلا لقائدة المشروع. سيتم الاحتفاظ بجميع ملفات البيانات على خادم آمن يلي لوائح متطلبات حماية البيانات. سيتم استخدام عناوين البريد الإلكتروني فقط لإرسال استبيان ثانٍ ودعوتك لإجراء مقابلة فردية. سنستخدم رقم المعرف لربط الإجابات من الاستطلاع الأول والثاني. لن تتم مشاركة ملف عناوين البريد الإلكتروني مع أي شخص.

لقد أشرت إلى أنني على استعداد للاتصال بي بشأن الجولة الثانية من الاستطلاع وإدخال عنوان بريدي الإلكتروني. لقد غيرت رأيي. هل يمكنك إزالة عنواني من الملف؟

نعم نستطيع. يرجى الاتصال بالدكتورة ليا مولر فونك (lea.mueller-funk@donau-uni.ac.at) وستتم إزالة عنوان بريدك الإلكتروني.

بمن يمكنني الاتصال إذا كانت لدي أسئلة أو مخاوف؟

يمكنك الاتصال بـ د. ليا مولر فونك (lea.mueller-funk@donau-uni.ac.at) أو رئيس لجنة الأخلاقيات بجامعة التعليم المستمر كرييس (ethikkommission@donau-uni.ac.at).

Annex 3: To-do file (cleaning survey)

describe
summarize

change labels of variables

tab refurl

sort refurl

replace refurl = "Facebook" if refurl == "android-app://m.facebook.com/"

replace refurl = "Facebook" if refurl == "http://m.facebook.com"

replace refurl = "Facebook" if refurl == "https://l.facebook.com/"

replace refurl = "Facebook" if refurl == "https://lm.facebook.com/"

replace refurl = "Facebook" if refurl == "https://lm.facebook.com/"

replace refurl = "Facebook" if refurl == "https://m.facebook.com/"

replace refurl = "Facebook" if refurl == "http://m.facebook.com/"

replace refurl = "Instagram" if refurl == "http://instagram.com/"

replace refurl = "Instagram" if refurl == "https://www.instagram.com/"

replace refurl = "Project website" if refurl == "https://syreality.com/"

replace refurl = "University LimeSurvey website" if refurl == "https://uwk-krems.limesurvey.net/358395"

replace refurl = "University LimeSurvey website" if refurl == "https://uwk-krems.limesurvey.net/358395?lang=ar&fbclid=IwAR072-

VW19usUy9ESod5vx3iTqXlGmIK0k6iVJXfdBa00wUWZGEOIK-hzh0"

replace refurl = "University LimeSurvey website" if refurl == "https://uwk-

krems.limesurvey.net/358395?lang=ar&fbclid=PAAaaaMP5LO2GFyGXJ9bF0_PhVY3Yv1mqwUoMgPcafqK6Zxz38Va5myn6q_v8"

replace refurl = "University LimeSurvey website" if refurl == "https://uwk-

krems.limesurvey.net/358395?lang=ar&fbclid=PAAabUwUpsyFzyPx03INDBuv4xntM9oKdPky2K4_JAeYLRKn7tHPxk26rCZpo_aem_AeN7Lnft6x0p_r3vrh4lgrU-

4WuPsSNKeJyEsGfr11N6uuAIHrQMaC5EjiEYlgTFGGsUQLx28ct5KACPItoWHvAKzaOGVtPBrS1R0WizYMP0nRf2OlrXkMyNy541d_SsVEY"

label variable E1 "born in Syria"

tab E1

label variable E2 "Syrian citizenship"

tab E2

label variable E3 "year of birth"

tab E3

label variable E4 "last departure Syria after 2011"

tab E4

```
label variable E5 "current living country"  
tab E5
```

```
label variable E6 "year since living in current country"  
drop END5
```

```
label variable DEM1 "gender"  
tab DEM1
```

```
label variable DEM2 "highest level of education completed"  
tab DEM2
```

```
label variable DEM3 "marital status"  
tab DEM3
```

```
gen DEM3_cat = .  
label variable DEM3_cat "marital status"  
replace DEM3_cat = 1 if DEM3 == "MS1"  
replace DEM3_cat = 2 if DEM3 == "MS2"  
replace DEM3_cat = 3 if DEM3 == "MS3"  
replace DEM3_cat = 97 if DEM3 == "97"  
tab DEM3_cat  
label define DEM3lbl 1 "single" 2 "married or in a long-term relationship" 3 "divorced or widowed" 97  
"don't know" 98 "prefer not to say"  
label values DEM3_cat DEM3lbl  
tab DEM3_cat  
drop DEM3  
rename DEM3_cat DEM3  
tab DEM3
```

```
label variable DEM4 "children"  
tab DEM4
```

```
drop ASP0
```

```
label variable ASP1 "key life event in past 15 years"  
label variable ASP2 "educational aspirations"  
label variable ASP3_1 "educational aspirations before 2011"  
label variable ASP3_2 "educational aspirations between 2011 and arrival Europe"  
label variable ASP3_3 "educational aspirations since arrival in Europe"  
label variable ASP4 "education interrupted because of war"
```

label variable ASP4 "education interrupted because of war"

drop ASP00

label variable ASP5a_1 "social aspirations (starting family) in 2010"

label variable ASP5a_2 "social aspirations (living together) in 2010"

label variable ASP5a_3 "social aspirations (romantic relationship not approved of family) in 2010"

label variable ASP5a_4 "social aspirations (end relationship) in 2010"

label variable ASP5a_5 "social aspirations (improve relationship) in 2010"

label variable ASP5a_7 "no social aspirations in 2010"

label variable ASP5a_other "other social aspiration in 2010"

label variable ASP5b_1 "social aspirations (starting family) between 2011 and arrival in Europe"

label variable ASP5b_2 "social aspirations (living together) between 2011 and arrival in Europe"

label variable ASP5b_3 "social aspirations (romantic relationship not approved of family) between 2011 and arrival in Europe"

label variable ASP5b_4 "social aspirations (end relationship) between 2011 and arrival in Europe"

label variable ASP5b_5 "social aspirations (improve relationship) between 2011 and arrival in Europe"

label variable ASP5b_7 "no social aspirations between 2011 and arrival in Europe"

label variable ASP5b_other "other social aspiration between 2011 and arrival in Europe"

label variable ASP5c_1 "social aspirations (starting family) since arrival in Europe"

label variable ASP5c_2 "social aspirations (living together) since arrival in Europe"

label variable ASP5c_3 "social aspirations (romantic relationship not approved of family) since arrival in Europe"

label variable ASP5c_4 "social aspirations (end relationship) since arrival in Europe"

label variable ASP5c_5 "social aspirations (improve relationship) since arrival in Europe"

label variable ASP5c_7 "no social aspirations since arrival in Europe"

label variable ASP5c_other "other social aspiration since arrival in Europe"

label variable ASP6a "professional aspiration in 2010"

label variable ASP6b "type of professional aspiration in 2010"

label variable ASP6c "professional aspiration between 2011 and arrival in Europe"

label variable ASP6d "type of professional aspiration between 2011 and arrival in Europe"

label variable ASP6e "professional aspiration since arrival in Europe"

label variable ASP6f "type of professional aspiration since arrival in Europe"

label variable ASP7 "aspiration for social and political change"

label variable ASP8_1 "aspiration for social and political change before 2011"

label variable ASP8_2 "aspiration for social and political change between 2011 and arrival in Europe"

label variable ASP8_3 "aspiration for social and political change since arrival in Europe"

label variable ASP9 "enacting social and political change"

label variable ASP10_1 "participation in local groups and youth initiatives"

label variable ASP10_2 "participation in civil society organisation"

label variable ASP10_3 "changed social norms"

label variable ASP10_4 "voiced political opinion publicly"

label variable ASP10_5 "joined political party"

label variable ASP10_6 "participation in political movement"

label variable ASP10_7 "joined armed group"

label variable ASP10_8 "created support networks"

label variable ASP10_98 "prefer not to say how I enacted change"

label variable ASP10_other "enacted change in another way"

label variable ASP11 "interest in politics now"

label variable ASP12 "following politics in Syria"

label variable ASP13 "following politics in current country"

label variable FEMACT1 "enacting gender equality"

label variable FEMACT2_1 "enacting gender equality prior 2011"

label variable FEMACT2_2 "enacting gender equality between 2011 and departure in Europe"

label variable FEMACT2_3 "enacting gender equality since arrival in Europe"

label variable FEMACT3_1 "motive: witnessed inequality"

label variable FEMACT3_2 "motive: experienced discrimination in Syria as woman"

label variable FEMACT3_3 "motive: experienced discrimination abroad as woman"

label variable FEMACT3_4 "motive: training in Syria"

label variable FEMACT3_5 "motive: training abroad"

label variable FEMACT3_6 "motive: read feminist books"

label variable FEMACT3_7 "motive: worked for feminist organisation inside Syria"

label variable FEMACT3_8 "motive: worked for feminist organisation outside Syria "

label variable FEMACT3_9 "motive: inspiring feminist friend"

label variable FEMACT3_other "other motive"

label variable FEMACT4 "self-identification feminist"

drop D0

label variable D1 "place of living (governorate) in 2010"

label variable D2 "place of living (urban/rural) in 2010"

label variable D3 "internal displacement in Syria after 2011"

label variable D4 "place of living (area of control) after 2011"

label variable D4_other "other place of living (area of control) after 2011"

tab D4

replace D4 = "5" if D4 == "-oth-"

destring D4, gen(D4_num)

tab D4_num

label define D4lbl 1 "regime" 2 "opposition" 3 "ISIS" 4 "Autonomous Administration of North and East Syria" 5 "other" 6 "did not live in Syria after 2011" 97 "don't know" 98 "prefer not to say"

label values D4_num D4lbl

tab D4_num

drop D4

rename D4_num D4

tab D4

label variable D5 "move to different area of control after 2011"

label variable D6_1 "external displacement reason_personal threat"

label variable D6_2 "external displacement reason_bombings"

label variable D6_3 "external displacement reason_freedom of expression"

label variable D6_4 "external displacement reason_wanting neutrality"

label variable D6_5 "external displacement reason_economic situation"

label variable D6_6 "external displacement reason_house destroyed"

label variable D6_7 "external displacement reason_join family abroad"

label variable D6_8 "external displacement reason_no access education"

label variable D6_9 "external displacement reason_no access health services"

label variable D6_other "external displacement reason_other reason"

label variable D6_98 "external displacement reason_prefer not to say"

label variable D7a "living in other country before current country for more than one year after 2011"

label variable D7b_1 "Turkey host country after 2011"

label variable D7b_2 "Jordan host country after 2011"

label variable D7b_3 "Lebanon host country after 2011"

label variable D7b_4 "Egypt host country after 2011"

label variable D7b_5 "Saudia Arabia host country after 2011"

label variable D7b_6 "UAE host country after 2011"

label variable D7b_7 "Greece host country after 2011"

label variable D7b_8 "Italy host country after 2011"

label variable D7b_9 "Hungary host country after 2011"

label variable D7b_10 "Austria host country after 2011"

label variable D7b_11 "Germany host country after 2011"

label variable D7b_12 "Netherlands host country after 2011"

label variable D7b_13 "Sweden host country after 2011"

label variable D7b_98 "host country after 2011 (prefer not to say)"

label variable D7b_other "Other host country after 2011"

```
label variable D8 "current place of living"
label variable D9 "current legal status"
label variable D9_other "current legal status (other)"
label variable D10 "year of granting asylum/receiving residency"
label variable D11 "frequency contact family/friends Syria"
label variable D12 "frequency social media use"
label variable D13 "financial responsibility for family outside EU"

label variable POL1 "opinion about life for Syrians in Europe"
label variable POL2 "opinion about assistance for Syrians in host country"
```

```
drop MIG0
```

```
label variable MIG1 "stay aspiration in the past"
label variable MIG2_1 "Turkey stay aspirations in the past"
label variable MIG2_2 "Jordan stay aspirations in the past"
label variable MIG2_3 "Lebanon stay aspirations in the past"
label variable MIG2_4 "Egypt stay aspirations in the past"
label variable MIG2_5 "Saudia stay aspirations in the past"
label variable MIG2_6 "UAE stay aspirations in the past"
label variable MIG2_7 "Greece stay aspirations in the past"
label variable MIG2_8 "Italy stay aspirations in the past"
label variable MIG2_9 "Hungary stay aspirations in the past"
label variable MIG2_10 "Austria stay aspirations in the past"
label variable MIG2_11 "Germany stay aspirations in the past"
label variable MIG2_12 "Netherlands stay aspirations in the past"
label variable MIG2_13 "Sweden stay aspirations in the past"
label variable MIG2_other "Other country stay aspirations in the past"
label variable MIG3 "family in host country prior to arrival"
label variable MIG4 "migration aspirations in next 5 years"
tab MIG4
```

```
label variable MIG5 "country migration aspirations in next 5 years"
replace MIG5 = "83" if MIG5 == "-oth-"
tab MIG5
```

```
gen MIG5_cat = .
label variable MIG5_cat "country migration aspirations in next 5 years"
replace MIG5_cat = 1 if MIG5 == "1"
replace MIG5_cat = 2 if MIG5 == "2"
replace MIG5_cat = 3 if MIG5 == "3"
replace MIG5_cat = 4 if MIG5 == "4"
```

replace MIG5_cat = 5 if MIG5 == "5"
replace MIG5_cat = 6 if MIG5 == "6"
replace MIG5_cat = 7 if MIG5 == "7"
replace MIG5_cat = 8 if MIG5 == "8"
replace MIG5_cat = 9 if MIG5 == "9"
replace MIG5_cat = 10 if MIG5 == "10"
replace MIG5_cat = 11 if MIG5 == "11"
replace MIG5_cat = 12 if MIG5 == "12"
replace MIG5_cat = 13 if MIG5 == "13"
replace MIG5_cat = 14 if MIG5 == "14"
replace MIG5_cat = 15 if MIG5 == "15"
replace MIG5_cat = 16 if MIG5 == "16"
replace MIG5_cat = 17 if MIG5 == "17"
replace MIG5_cat = 18 if MIG5 == "18"
replace MIG5_cat = 19 if MIG5 == "19"
replace MIG5_cat = 20 if MIG5 == "20"
replace MIG5_cat = 21 if MIG5 == "21"
replace MIG5_cat = 22 if MIG5 == "22"
replace MIG5_cat = 23 if MIG5 == "23"
replace MIG5_cat = 24 if MIG5 == "24"
replace MIG5_cat = 25 if MIG5 == "25"
replace MIG5_cat = 26 if MIG5 == "26"
replace MIG5_cat = 27 if MIG5 == "27"
replace MIG5_cat = 28 if MIG5 == "28"
replace MIG5_cat = 29 if MIG5 == "29"
replace MIG5_cat = 30 if MIG5 == "30"
replace MIG5_cat = 31 if MIG5 == "31"
replace MIG5_cat = 32 if MIG5 == "32"
replace MIG5_cat = 33 if MIG5 == "33"
replace MIG5_cat = 34 if MIG5 == "34"
replace MIG5_cat = 35 if MIG5 == "35"
replace MIG5_cat = 36 if MIG5 == "36"
replace MIG5_cat = 37 if MIG5 == "37"
replace MIG5_cat = 38 if MIG5 == "38"
replace MIG5_cat = 39 if MIG5 == "39"
replace MIG5_cat = 40 if MIG5 == "40"
replace MIG5_cat = 41 if MIG5 == "41"
replace MIG5_cat = 42 if MIG5 == "42"
replace MIG5_cat = 43 if MIG5 == "43"
replace MIG5_cat = 44 if MIG5 == "44"
replace MIG5_cat = 45 if MIG5 == "45"
replace MIG5_cat = 46 if MIG5 == "46"

```
replace MIG5_cat = 47 if MIG5 == "47"  
replace MIG5_cat = 48 if MIG5 == "48"  
replace MIG5_cat = 49 if MIG5 == "49"  
replace MIG5_cat = 50 if MIG5 == "50"  
replace MIG5_cat = 51 if MIG5 == "51"  
replace MIG5_cat = 52 if MIG5 == "52"  
replace MIG5_cat = 53 if MIG5 == "53"  
replace MIG5_cat = 54 if MIG5 == "54"  
replace MIG5_cat = 55 if MIG5 == "55"  
replace MIG5_cat = 56 if MIG5 == "56"  
replace MIG5_cat = 57 if MIG5 == "57"  
replace MIG5_cat = 58 if MIG5 == "58"  
replace MIG5_cat = 59 if MIG5 == "59"  
replace MIG5_cat = 60 if MIG5 == "60"  
replace MIG5_cat = 61 if MIG5 == "61"  
replace MIG5_cat = 62 if MIG5 == "62"  
replace MIG5_cat = 63 if MIG5 == "63"  
replace MIG5_cat = 64 if MIG5 == "64"  
replace MIG5_cat = 65 if MIG5 == "65"  
replace MIG5_cat = 66 if MIG5 == "66"  
replace MIG5_cat = 67 if MIG5 == "67"  
replace MIG5_cat = 68 if MIG5 == "68"  
replace MIG5_cat = 69 if MIG5 == "69"  
replace MIG5_cat = 70 if MIG5 == "70"  
replace MIG5_cat = 71 if MIG5 == "71"  
replace MIG5_cat = 72 if MIG5 == "72"  
replace MIG5_cat = 73 if MIG5 == "73"  
replace MIG5_cat = 74 if MIG5 == "74"  
replace MIG5_cat = 75 if MIG5 == "75"  
replace MIG5_cat = 76 if MIG5 == "76"  
replace MIG5_cat = 77 if MIG5 == "77"  
replace MIG5_cat = 78 if MIG5 == "78"  
replace MIG5_cat = 79 if MIG5 == "79"  
replace MIG5_cat = 80 if MIG5 == "80"  
replace MIG5_cat = 81 if MIG5 == "81"  
replace MIG5_cat = 82 if MIG5 == "82"  
replace MIG5_cat = 83 if MIG5 == "83"  
replace MIG5_cat = 97 if MIG5 == "97"  
replace MIG5_cat = 98 if MIG5 == "98"  
tab MIG5_cat
```

```

label define MIG5lbl 1 "Ethiopia" 2 "Azerbaijan" 3 "Jordan" 4 "Armenia" 5 "Spain" 6
    "Australia" 7 "Estonia" 8 "Afghanistan" 9 "Albania" 10 "Germany" 11 "United Arab
Emirates" 12 "Indonesia" 13 "Ukraine" 14 "Iran" 15 "Ireland" 16 "Iceland" 17 "Italy"
18 "Pakistan" 19 "Bahrain" 20 "Portugal" 21 "Brunei" 22 "Belgium" 23 "Bulgaria" 24
    "Bosnia and Herzegovina" 25 "Poland" 26 "Belarus" 27 "Turkmenistan" 28
    "Tunisia" 29 "Montenegro" 30 "Algeria" 31 "Czech Republic" 32 "South Africa"
33 "South Sudan" 34 "Georgia" 35 "Djibouti" 36 "Denmark" 37 "Qatar" 38
    "Turkey" 39 "Russia" 40 "Romania" 41 "Oman" 42 "Slovakia" 43 "Slovenia" 44
    "Singapore" 45 "Sweden" 46 "Switzerland" 47 "Serbia" 48 "Iraq" 49
    "France" 50 "Palestine" 51 "Finland" 52 "Philippines" 53 "Cyprus" 54 "Croatia" 55
    "Canada" 56 "Kosovo" 57 "Kuwait" 58 "Latvia" 59 "Lebanon" 60 "Luxembourg" 61
    "Libya" 62 "Lithuania" 63 "Liechtenstein" 64 "Malta" 65 "Malaysia" 66 "Egypt"
67 "Morocco" 68 "Macedonia" 69 "Saudi Arabia" 70 "United Kingdom" 71
    "Mauritania" 72 "Moldova" 73 "Monaco" 74 "Norway" 75 "Austria" 76 "New Zealand"
77 "India" 78 "Hungary" 79 "The Netherlands" 80 "United States of America" 81
    "Yemen" 82 "Greece" 97 "Don't know" 98 "Prefer not to say" 83 "Other"

```

```
label list MIG5lbl
```

```
label values MIG5lbl MIG5_cat
```

```
tab MIG5_cat
```

```
tab MIG5
```

```
drop MIG5
```

```
rename MIG5_cat MIG5
```

```
tab MIG5
```

```
label variable MIG5_other "country migration aspirations in next 5 years (other)"
```

```
tab MIG6
```

```
label variable MIG6 "migration preparations"
```

```
tab MIG7
```

```
label variable MIG7 "internal migration aspirations"
```

```
tab MIG8
```

```
label variable MIG8 "return aspirations in next 5 years"
```

```
tab MIG9
```

```
label variable MIG9 "return considerations in the past"
```

```
tab MIG10
```

```
label variable MIG10 "future return aspirations if safe"
```

```
tab MIG11
```

```
label variable MIG10 "conditions in Syria necessary for safe return"
```

```
tab DEM5
```

```
label variable DEM5 "current location spouse/partner"
```

```
gen DEM5_cat = .
```

```
label variable DEM5_cat "current location spouse/partner"
```

```
replace DEM5_cat = 1 if DEM5 == "1"
```

```
replace DEM5_cat = 2 if DEM5 == "2"
```

```
replace DEM5_cat = 3 if DEM5 == "3"
```

```
replace DEM5_cat = 3 if DEM5 == "-oth-"
```

```
replace DEM5_cat = 97 if DEM5 == "97"
```

```
replace DEM5_cat = 98 if DEM5 == "98"
```

```
tab DEM5_cat
```

```
label define DEM5lbl 1 "in same household as me" 2 "same country as me, but not with me" 3 "in  
another country" 97 "don't know" 98 "prefer not to say"
```

```
label values DEM5_cat DEM5lbl
```

```
tab DEM5_cat
```

```
drop DEM5
```

```
rename DEM5_cat DEM5
```

```
tab DEM5
```

```
drop DEM5_other
```

```
tab DEM6
```

```
label variable DEM6 "children living with respondent"
```

```
tab DEM7
```

```
replace DEM7 = "10" if DEM7 == "-oth-"
```

```
destring DEM7, gen(DEM7_num)
```

```
tab DEM7_num
```

```
label define DEM7lbl 98 "Prefer not to say" 1 "Muslim Sunni" 2 "Muslim Shia" 3 "Muslim Alawi" 4 "Other  
Muslim" 5 "Druze" 6 "Yazidi" 7 "Christian" 8 "Jewish" 9 "No religion (atheist)" 10 "Other" 97 "Don't know"
```

```
label values DEM7_num DEM7lbl
```

```
drop DEM7
```

```
rename DEM7_num DEM7
```

```
label variable DEM7 "religion"
```

```
label variable DEM7_other "religion (other)"
```

```
tab DEM7_other
```

tab DEM8_1
label variable DEM8_1 "mother tongue Arabic"

tab DEM8_2
label variable DEM8_2 "mother tongue Kurdish"

tab DEM8_3
label variable DEM8_3 "mother tongue Turkish"

tab DEM8_4
label variable DEM8_4 "mother tongue Armenian"

tab DEM8_other
label variable DEM8_other "mother tongue (other)"

tab DEM9_1
label variable DEM9_1 "other language skills (Arabic)"

tab DEM9_2
label variable DEM9_2 "other language skills (Kurdish)"

tab DEM9_3
label variable DEM9_3 "other language skills (Turkish)"

tab DEM9_4
label variable DEM9_4 "other language skills (Armenian)"

tab DEM9_5
label variable DEM9_5 "other language skills (English)"

tab DEM9_6
label variable DEM9_6 "other language skills (French)"

tab DEM9_7
label variable DEM9_7 "other language skills (German)"

tab DEM9_8
label variable DEM9_8 "other language skills (Dutch)"

tab DEM9_9
label variable DEM9_9 "other language skills (Greek)"

tab DEM9_10

label variable DEM9_10 "no other language skills"

tab DEM9_other

label variable DEM9_other "other language skills (specified)"

tab WPW1

label variable WPW1 "ever done paid work"

tab WPW2

label variable WPW2 "longest paid job (type)"

label define professionslbl 1 "Professional and technical" 2 "Higher administrator" 3 "Clerical" 4 "Sales" 5 "Service" 6 "Skilled worker" 7 "Semi-skilled worker" 8 "Unskilled worker" 9 "Farm worker" 10 "Farm proprietor, farm manager"

label values WPW2 professionslbl

tab WPW3

label variable WPW3 "longest paid job was main job before 2011"

tab WPW4

label variable WPW4 "main job before 2011 (type)"

label define professionslbl2 1 "Professional and technical" 2 "Higher administrator" 3 "Clerical" 4 "Sales" 5 "Service" 6 "Skilled worker" 7 "Semi-skilled worker" 8 "Unskilled worker" 9 "Farm worker" 10 "Farm proprietor, farm manager" 11 "no job before 2011"

label values WPW4 professionslbl2

tab WPW5

label variable WPW5 "longest job since leaving Syria (type)"

label define professionslbl3 1 "Professional and technical" 2 "Higher administrator" 3 "Clerical" 4 "Sales" 5 "Service" 6 "Skilled worker" 7 "Semi-skilled worker" 8 "Unskilled worker" 9 "Farm worker" 10 "Farm proprietor, farm manager" 11 "no job in this period"

label values WPW5 professionslbl3

tab WPW6

label variable WPW6 "current job situation"

label define WPW6lbl 1 "full-time employment" 2 "part-time employment" 3 "minimal or irregular employment" 4 "professional training or internship" 5 "temporarily out of work" 6 "responsible for caring for family members, shopping and housework" 7 "retired/pensioner" 8 "student"

label values WPW6 WPW6lbl

tab WPW7

label variable WPW7 "current job (type)"

label values WPW7 professionslbl

tab WPW8

label variable WPW8 "spouse/partner paid work"

tab WPW9

label variable WPW9 "longest job spouse/partner (type)"

label values WPW9 professionslbl

tab WPW10

label variable WPW10 "job situation father at 14"

tab WPW11

label variable WPW11 "job father at 14 (type)"

label define WPW11lbl 1 "Professional and technical" 2 "Higher administrator" 3 "Clerical" 4 "Sales" 5 "Service" 6 "Skilled worker" 7 "Semi-skilled worker" 8 "Unskilled worker" 9 "Farm worker" 10 "Farm proprietor, farm manager" 97 "Don't know"

label values WPW11 WPW11lbl

tab WPW12

label variable WPW12 "financial situation 2010"

label define WPW12lbl 1 "no money for food" 2 "only money for most necessary things" 3 "borrowing money to buy expensive things" 4 "buying car was difficult" 5 "buying home was beyond means" 6 "could afford anything" 97 "Don't know" 98 "Prefer not to say"

label values WPW12 WPW12lbl

tab WPW13_1

label variable WPW13_1 "house ownership in 2010"

tab WPW13_2

label variable WPW13_2 "business ownership in 2010"

tab WPW13_3

label variable WPW13_3 "land ownership in 2010"

tab WPW13_4

label variable WPW13_4 "no property in 2010"

drop WPW13_97

tab WPW14

label variable WPW14 "looting, confiscation or destruction of property after 2011"

tab WPW15

label variable WPW15 "loss documentation property after 2011"

tab WPW16

label variable WPW16 "financial situation when leaving Syria"

label values WPW16 WPW12lbl

tab WPW17

label variable WPW17 "financial situation since arrival current host country"

tab WPW18

label variable WPW18 "social class scale prior 2011 (self-assessment)"

tab WPW19

label variable WPW19 "social class scale when leaving Syria (self-assessment)"

tab WPW20

label variable WPW20 "social class scale current host country (self-assessment)"

tab SAT1a

label variable SAT1a "quality life"

tab SAT1b

label variable SAT1b "life satisfaction"

tab SAT2

label variable SAT2 "satisfaction mental well-being"

tab SAT3

label variable SAT3 "hope personal future in Europe"

tab SAT4

label variable SAT4 "hope future of Syria"

tab SAT5

label variable SAT5 "activities to feel good"

tab END1

label variable END1 "overall impression survey"

tab END2

label variable END2 "future participation in second wave"

tab END3

label variable END3 "willingness participation qualitative interview"

tab END4_1

label variable END4_1 "email address"

tab END4_1comment

label variable END4_1comment "email address"

drop END4_1

rename END4_1comment END4_1

tab END4_1

tab END4_2

label variable END4_2 "Facebook"

drop END4_2

tab END4_2comment

label variable END4_2comment "Facebook name respondent"

rename END4_2comment END4_2

tab END4_3

label variable END4_3 "by phone"

drop END4_3

tab END4_3comment

label variable END4_3comment "phone number"

rename END4_3comment END4_3

describe

*double check filter questions for target population to doublecheck LimeSurvey settings, reduced from 4876 to 3,968 observations

tab E1

tab E2

*4642; 146 don't know

tab E1 E2

*set all further responses to NA if respondents do not know if they have Syrian citizenship and were not born in Syria; dropped 3 observations in subsequent responses

```
foreach var of varlist_all {
  if "`var'" != "E2" {
    replace `var' = . if E2 == 97
  }
}
```

```
ds, has(type string)
foreach var in `r(varlist)' {
  if "`var'" != "E2" {
    replace `var' = "" if E2 == 97
  }
}
```

```
tab E3
*4277 --> changed now to 4,274
```

```
tab E4
*4231
```

```
tab E5
*3968 - 10 not target population
```

```
tab E6
*3873 part of target population
```

```
****checking for duplicates****
```

```
***IP address****
```

```
*address missing values
replace ipaddr = "missing" if ipaddr == ""
replace ipaddr = "NA" if ipaddr == "missing"
```

```
duplicates report ipaddr
*146 missing IP addresses
**197 duplicated IP addresses
```

```
duplicates list ipaddr
duplicates tag ipaddr, generate(dup_tag)
list ipaddr if dup_tag > 0 in 1/200
```

```
sort ipaddr
```

```
list ipaddr if dup_tag > 0
browse ipaddr if dup_tag > 0
```

```
***new variable to check time spent on survey in minutes***
```

```
describe startdate
describe datestamp
```

```
gen duration_min = (datestamp - startdate)/(1000*60)
label variable duration_min "duration spent on survey"
tab duration_min
describe duration_min
summarize duration_min
summarize duration_min, detail
```

```
*mean 15 min
```

```
drop if id == 666
drop if id == 1335
drop if id == 317
drop if id == 1502
drop if id == 619
drop if id == 1912
drop if id == 4032
drop if id == 4448
drop if id == 3706
drop if id == 3160
drop if id == 1878
drop if id == 73
drop if id == 2278
drop if id == 746
drop if id == 3296
drop if id == 1422
drop if id == 4696
drop if id == 1476
drop if id == 3343
drop if id == 3511
drop if id == 642
drop if id == 2433
drop if id == 1185
drop if id == 3366
```

drop if id == 2112
drop if id == 2140
drop if id == 4325
drop if id == 2894
drop if id == 2719
drop if id == 4597
drop if id == 4431
drop if id == 1630
drop if id == 3510
drop if id == 1425
drop if id == 2011
drop if id == 3338
drop if id == 183
drop if id == 3496
drop if id == 179
drop if id == 1972
drop if id == 643
drop if id == 1824
drop if id == 1386
drop if id == 3637
drop if id == 3991
drop if id == 873
drop if id == 4099
drop if id == 936
drop if id == 2695
drop if id == 2057
drop if id == 2718
drop if id == 1546
drop if id == 624
drop if id == 832
drop if id == 1092
drop if id == 1278
drop if id == 1295
drop if id == 4396
drop if id == 4397
drop if id == 535
drop if id == 4807
drop if id == 4102
drop if id == 4731
drop if id == 4007
drop if id == 2211
drop if id == 11

drop if id == 1070
drop if id == 1408
drop if id == 934
drop if id == 2485
drop if id == 4751
drop if id == 2151
drop if id == 4524
drop if id == 17
drop if id == 3047
drop if id == 1918
drop if id == 1634
drop if id == 3479
drop if id == 253
drop if id == 2147
drop if id == 3888
drop if id == 3262
drop if id == 443
drop if id == 2618
drop if id == 375
drop if id == 3237
drop if id == 4281
drop if id == 1449
drop if id == 470
drop if id == 1339
drop if id == 1814
drop if id == 2731
drop if id == 428
drop if id == 2790
drop if id == 321
drop if id == 579
drop if id == 2270
drop if id == 37
drop if id == 4130
drop if id == 3436
drop if id == 827
drop if id == 1987
drop if id == 4716
drop if id == 3964
drop if id == 2261
drop if id == 559
drop if id == 4537
drop if id == 4237

drop if id == 3676
drop if id == 995
drop if id == 65
drop if id == 379
drop if id == 288
drop if id == 205
drop if id == 638
drop if id == 638
drop if id == 1346
drop if id == 2955
drop if id == 113
drop if id == 276
drop if id == 2667
drop if id == 4416
drop if id == 1362
drop if id == 786
drop if id == 1146
drop if id == 2764
drop if id == 2067
drop if id == 3986
drop if id == 4210
drop if id == 3258
drop if id == 2570
drop if id == 4835
drop if id == 1961
drop if id == 4316
drop if id == 1988
drop if id == 4818
drop if id == 4248
drop if id == 820
drop if id == 412
drop if id == 3922
drop if id == 3175
drop if id == 244
drop if id == 3820
drop if id == 2113
drop if id == 2094
drop if id == 1526
drop if id == 528
drop if id == 4046
drop if id == 2800
drop if id == 1772

drop if id == 4019
drop if id == 2445
drop if id == 1742
drop if id == 3014
drop if id == 1180
drop if id == 4642
drop if id == 2884
drop if id == 3720
drop if id == 2451
drop if id == 105
drop if id == 61
drop if id == 3342
drop if id == 4040
drop if id == 1730
drop if id == 562

***email address

duplicates report END4_1

*address missing values

replace END4_1 = "missing" if END4_1 == ""

*3164 missing email addresses (missing)

***574 did not want to indicate email addresses (0)

**5 duplicates; had different IP addresses - not sure why people answered it several times

duplicates list END4_1

duplicates tag END4_1, generate(dup_tag1)

list END4_1 if dup_tag1 > 0 in 1/200

sort END4_1

list END4_1 if dup_tag1 > 0

browse END4_1 if dup_tag1 > 0

drop if id == 3427

drop if id == 4382

drop if id == 3711

drop if id == 3418

drop if id == 4123

***phone number

duplicates report END4_3

replace END4_3 = "missing" if END4_3 == ""

*3164 missing phone numbers

***1180 did not want to indicate phone number

```
duplicates list END4_3
duplicates tag END4_3, generate(dup_tag2)
list END4_3 if dup_tag2 > 0
```

```
sort END4_3
list END4_3 if dup_tag2 > 0
browse END4_3 if dup_tag2 > 0
***one duplicated phone number, different IP addresses
```

```
drop if id == 4293
```

```
***Make new variable for survey responses
```

```
***I added a variable differentiating four response categories:
```

```
***1) Opened survey but did not answer any questions – if E1 was missing
```

```
***2) Opened survey but was not part of target group (determined based on replies to filter questions):
either not born in Syria, not having Syrian citizenship (or don't know ); not born between 1957 and 1996,
not left Syria after 2011; not living in either Greece, Austria, Germany or Netherlands (E1-E5)
```

```
***3) Part of target group, answered several questions but did not complete survey
```

```
***4) Part of target group and completed survey (measured as answering questions up to
***question before SAT4)
```

```
*4706 observations
```

```
tab lastpage
```

```
sort lastpage
```

```
browse id lastpage E1 ASP1 SAT4 SAT5 END1 END2 END3
```

```
***not clear what -1 corresponds to
```

```
***lastpage can still be missing if respondents replied to some questions
```

```
*spike (482 observations) around value 12 --> corresponds to when we ask about life aspirations (after
filtering questions)
```

```
***What is -1??? saving mistake
```

```
generate respcat = .
```

```
label variable respcat "response categories"
```

```
tab respcat
```

```
***target population and stopped before final questions (SAT4)
```

```
replace respcat = 3 if E1 == 0 & E2 == 1
```

```
replace respcat = 3 if E1 == 1 & E2 == 0
```

```
replace respcat = 3 if E1 == 1 & E2 == 1
```

```
replace respcat = 3 if E3 == 1957-1996
```

```
replace respcat = 3 if E4 == 1
replace respcat = 3 if E5 == 1-4
*3844 target population
```

```
***target population + if replied question SAT4 or after
***SAT4 = lastpage 96
***SAT5 = lastpage 97
*** END 1 = 100
recode respcat (3 = 4) if lastpage >= 96
*1947 completed, 1894 partly
```

```
**started survey but not target population
replace respcat = 2 if E1 == 0 & E2 == 0
replace respcat = 2 if E1 == 0 & E2 == 97
replace respcat = 2 if E1 == 0 & E2 == .
replace respcat = 2 if E3 == 999
replace respcat = 2 if E3 == .
replace respcat = 2 if E4 == 0
replace respcat = 2 if E4 == .
replace respcat = 2 if E5 == 5
replace respcat = 2 if E5 == .
*705
```

```
**did not fill out first question
replace respcat = 1 if E1 == .
*175
```

```
tab respcat
```

```
label define respcatlbl 1 "opened survey without answering any question" 2 "opened survey but not part
of target population" 3 "part of target group but did not complete survey" 4 "part of target group and
completed survey"
```

```
label values respcat respcatlbl
```

```
recode respcat (1=.) (2=.) (3=0) (4=1), gen(respstat1)
label variable respstat1 "response categories target population"
```

```
tab respstat1
```

```
label define respstat1lbl 0 "part of target group but did not complete survey" 1 "part of target group and
completed survey"
```

```
label values respstat1 respstat1lbl
```

```
****checking break-off patterns
```

```

tab respcat1
tab DEM1
tab DEM2
codebook DEM2

recode DEM2 (2=1) (3=2) (4=3) (5=3) (6=4) (7=5) (8=5) (9=5), gen(educ)
label variable educ "educational attainment simplified"
label define educlbl 1 "no formal education or primary" 2 "middle school" 3 "secondary school" 4
"technical post-secondary" 5 "university"
label values educ educlbl
tab educ
tab DEM1
logit respcat1 i.educ i.DEM1

****check for speeding

summarize duration_min
summarize duration_min, detail

***check survey length if survey filled out completely

tab duration_min if lastpage == 100
codebook respcat1

tab duration_min if respcat1 == 1
browse duration_min if respcat1 == 1
***no reponse below 7 minutes***
***checked observations below 10 for streamlining;
tab duration_min if respcat1 == 1 & duration_min < 10
browse if respcat1 == 1 & duration_min < 10
*responses looked legitimate
browse if respcat1 == 1
sort duration_min

***contact data second wave
tab END2

***contact qualitative interview
tab END3

tab END4_1
generate email = END4_1

```

```

label variable email "email address"
replace email = "" if email == "0"
replace email = "" if email == "missing"
replace email = "" if email == "."
replace email = "" if email == "لا يوجد"
replace email = "" if email == "للاسف مو ذاكرو كويس"
tab email
sort email
***965 email addresses

```

```

tab END4_2
generate FBcontact = END4_2
label variable FBcontact "Facebook name"
replace FBcontact = "" if FBcontact == "missing"
replace FBcontact = "" if FBcontact == "0"
replace FBcontact = "" if FBcontact == "."
sort FBcontact
tab FBcontact
*319 FB contacts

```

```

tab END4_3
generate phone = END4_3
label variable phone "phone number"
replace phone = "" if phone == "missing"
replace phone = "" if phone == "0"
replace phone = "" if phone == "."
replace phone = "" if phone == "لا أفضل"
sort phone
tab phone
***362 phone numbers

```

```

gen western_phone = phone
replace western_phone = substr(western_phone, ".", "0", .)
replace western_phone = substr(western_phone, "\", "1", .)
replace western_phone = substr(western_phone, "٢", "2", .)
replace western_phone = substr(western_phone, "٣", "3", .)
replace western_phone = substr(western_phone, "٤", "4", .)
replace western_phone = substr(western_phone, "٥", "5", .)
replace western_phone = substr(western_phone, "٦", "6", .)
replace western_phone = substr(western_phone, "٧", "7", .)
replace western_phone = substr(western_phone, "٨", "8", .)
replace western_phone = substr(western_phone, "٩", "9", .)

```

```
drop phone
rename western_phone phone
tab phone
label variable phone "phone number"
```

***Create 1) Contact Database which stores personal identifiers (name, email, phone, gender + unique participant ID (PID)); 2) Survey Response Database: which stores survey answers and metadata + PID

```
*contact database: id email FBcontact phone
```

```
browse id email FBcontact phone if END2 == 1 & email != "" | FB != "" | phone != ""
***then export as excel
```

```
***cleaning exported contact database
```

```
export excel id email FBcontact phone E5 using "Contact database_survey second wave.xlsx" if END2 ==
1, firstrow(variables)
*1660 observations
```

```
*delete observations with no contact data: drop if email == "" & FB == "" & phone == ""
*477 deleted
```

```
export excel id email FBcontact phone E5 using "Contact database_qualitative interviews.xlsx" if END3 ==
1, firstrow(variables)
```

```
*1264 observations*
```

```
***delete observations with no contact data: drop if email == "" & FB == "" & phone == ""
*236 deleted
```

```
***drop IP addresses; contact details in survey data file
```

```
drop dup_tag
drop dup_tag1
drop dup_tag2
drop ipaddr
drop END4_1
drop END4_2
drop END4_3
drop email
drop FBcontact
drop phone
```